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Agri-food and Tourism
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SELECTED PAPERS FROM THE 3rd NEEFOOD CONGRESS

Biodiversity

CalitaTerra

Sanogeneous Food

Sustainable Tourism and Hospitality

Ideas and Concepts

News

20-23 May 2015

3rd NEEFOOD CONGRESS

Global and Local Challenges in Food Science and
Technology

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Editor: Gaceu L.

EcoAgriTourism, in the light of its multidisciplinary character, is a wide-open journal which brings together the opinions of specialists from both academic and economic environment, fostering fruitful collaborations.

The journal's structure covers all aspects of the fields approached, the focus being on original and current researches with applications in agriculture, food industry and rural tourism. Collaborators may feel free to undertake biological and technical aspects as well as aspects with social, cultural and environmental impact. Information of general interest is also welcome for the agriecology-food-tourism axis.

Prof. Romulus Gruia Ph. D.

The Journal of EcoAgroTurism aims at approaching analyses, methodologies, options and references within the journal's framework.

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EDITORIAL

JUBILEE - 10 years issue of Journal of EcoAgriTourism

The EcoAgriTourism Journal fulfills this time 10 years of uninterrupted publication since 2005, in which, according to the proposed objective, were analyzed theoretically and were offered practical solutions for many aspects on the axis: *ecology-agriculture-food-tourism* and, by concentration, to impose the **phrase „eco-agri-tourism”**. The publication has proven to be a scientific source of information in agroecology, eco-biotechnology and food bioengineering, but also of applied agrotourism.

The EcoAgriTourism Journal, in the ten years of appearance, was open for cooperation with researchers, specialists, PhD, from Romania and from different countries of the world, so from 2008 the Journal appears in English, creating the possibility of being recognized abroad. Thus, along with high professionalism of the Scientific Board, made indexing possible in international databases (CABI, Global Health a.o.) increasing its visibility and citations potentiality. Through its topics (Biodiversity, CalitatTerra, Sanogeneous Food, Sustainable Tourism and specific issues of scientific events) it highlights the works contribution to the development of contemporary bioeconomy, structuring an unitary field thru multidisciplinary related items, which imposes the originality of this publication.

In the Journal can be found important names of researchers and university professors, and a series of papers presented at international congresses and conferences organized by Transilvania University of Brasov, through the Faculty of Food and Tourism and EBIOTEFA/Eco-biotechnology and Equipments in Agriculture and Food research center, and generously published by the Journal of EcoAgriTourism: The International Congress on Food NEEFood 2015, and the International **BIOATLAS** Conferences from **2008, 2010, 2012** and **2014**.

Continuing and enhancing the quality of articles (the average rejection being about 6,5 %), we hope that to the next jubilee of the EcoAgriTourism Journal to be in elite journals with relevant impact factor.

We congratulate with this occasion the academic teams from the university and the faculty who have contributed to the evolution of the journal with the publication of scientific papers, and colleagues from abroad in more than 25 countries, of foreign authors representing more than 60% and, not least, the editor en chief Prof. Habil. Eng. Liviu Gaceu PhD and the editorial board team.

Romulus GRUIA
Publication Director

Global Harmonization Initiative – GHI: Creating Connections, Building Consensus

One of GHI's priorities is to collect and communicate sound principles of food safety science to influencers and decision makers—from the general public and the press, to politicians, policymakers and regulatory authorities. The aim is to improve understanding and to better inform all stakeholders so that objective scientific concepts, not political expediency or media hype, become the basis of crafting meaningful, harmonized food safety legislation and regulation in all countries.

In addition to facilitating GHI Working Group meetings to build consensus within the scientific community, GHI is dedicated to creating scientific communications that are concise, easy to understand and can be translated into local languages. With the help of active volunteers in the communications field, GHI is working to develop a variety of educational materials, resources and platforms that are accessible by all around the globe. In addition, many GHI members contribute articles and interviews to national and international popular press outlets, and serve as official GHI Ambassadors to individual nations or regions, sharing and distributing information about GHI and harmonization at the local level.

GHI is working on :

- Identifying additional scientific organizations from all over the world to be invited to join the Initiative as member organizations
- Identifying individual food scientists, technologists and engineers, working in academia, food companies, institutes and scientific organizations, to be invited to join as individual scientific members
- Creating a position paper identifying and explaining the relevant issues affecting the global food industry
- Developing a strategy to find the shortest route to achieving global harmonization in concert with international standard-setting bodies such as the Codex Alimentarius Commission and the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) that are working on similar efforts.
- Developing a constitution and by laws

22 May 2015 | 9:00 - 11:00 am | NEEFood 2015

GHI President **Huub Lelieveld** led a **GHI General Meeting** on May 22 at the 3rd North and Eastern European Congress on Food (NEEFood 2015) in Brasov, Romania. The agenda will include:

- Brief introduction to GHI
- Mycotoxins and science (with **Mark Shamtsyan**, co-chair, GHI Mycotoxins Working Group)
- Toxins and food (Huub Lelieveld)
- General discussion

The meeting was free and open to all conference participants.

Huub Lelieveld

For more information about the Global Harmonization Initiative and its efforts to feed people and fuel innovation through harmonization of science-based global food safety regulations, please visit us online at www.globalharmonization.net.

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PLANT ENZYMES USED IN THE DIETARY SUPPLEMENT INDUSTRY

A COZEA^{* **}, V. TAMAS^{*}, M. NEAGU^{*}, C. NICA^{*}, SUCIU A.^{*}
A. MARCULESCU^{**}

Abstract: *Plants with phytotherapeutic favorable effect on the human body owe its present value of certain bioactive substances that are found in all species but only some of that have therapeutic proprieties. These highlights enzymes, substances that in small quantities play a key role in maintaining life, accelerating metabolic processes through decomposition and allowing food into assimilated nutrients that can be utilized for the cells and also substances to be removed. Enzymes are responsible for food digestion, energy production processes, defense mechanisms, and more. In the Hofigal company at Research and Development Department, we conducted research on determining the most important activity of digestive enzymes (amylase, protease, lipase) in several plant materials including the following: - sea buckthorn (*Hyppophae rhamnoides*) -fruit; - blackcurrant (*Ribes nigrum*)-leafs; -bitter cucumber (*Momordica charantia*) – leafs and offshoots, Aloe (*Aloe arborescens*) -leafs. Enzymatic analysis of selected plant material was conducted on Hofigal company with plants culture, organically grown and processed according to GMP standards, in order do not alter the pharmacodynamic action of the of interest active bio-substances and will be used in new enzyme supplements preparations.*

Keywords: *plant material, digestive enzymes, health*

1. Introduction

Enzymes, are proteins with complex structure, specific to microorganisms, plants, animals and humans, having an important role in the complexity of the mechanisms that take place in living organisms especially in digestive enzymes involved in converting nutrients into simple compounds substances nutrients. Enzymes action is similar to that of catalysts with the ability to determine a complex chemical reaction without altered themselves or being destroyed in the process [1-5]. In biochemical transformations that occur permanent in the body, works both endogenous and exogenous enzymes, so:

- Endogenous digestive enzymes are secreted by digestive glands with regulating role in digestion;

- Exogenous digestive enzymes, which have similar complementary role, that are procured from the outside, by eating vegetable or animal food.

Enzymes are vital for maintaining health, being responsible for each reaction in the human body. For example, when production of

pancreatic enzymes is insufficient, appears serious health problems. Vegetable enzymes are not indicated only for increase energy by strengthening the digestive system and the entire body. Some acute and chronic digestive diseases, sometimes, can be cured only by normalizing digestive function, following administration of enzyme preparations. [6-8]. Practical needs of enzymes in various diseases have led to the need to obtain large quantities of exogenous enzyme preparations with different catalytic activities. Unlike other living organisms, plant enzymes, are caught as in a net, plant fiber network which gives them a greater stability and they act in the human body as a product, acting retarded. "[9-15]. As a result, in the present are used advanced development techniques for investigating both health and factors with negative impact on health, attitude promoted by scientists for defending the body against these factors, by achieving food supplements. These are aimed at food deficiencies substituted by intake of essential nutrients, ensuring cell regeneration, and removing toxic substances to stimulate the immune defense capability of the human body [16-20]. This paper brings to the foreground the

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need and importance of natural enzyme food supplements that can be made from organically grown plants from greenhouse and those cultivated on field conditions.

2. Materials And Methods

Raw -Material used was obtained in controlled conditions in organic farming. Initially was rehabilitated land by growing a succession of different species of plants that extract substances from soil that can contaminate future harvests. Then, was cultivated plants, as sources of raw materials, without chemical fertilizers, herbicides, stimulants or other chemical treatments that may have contaminated crops and subsequently the products obtained. As a result, the plant material with, „eco "quality cultivation and processing, was approved in accordance with TUV and GMP rules. The plant material was used based on quality control and analysis rules using modern means for this purpose.

Plant material:

- buckthorn (*Hippophae rhamnoides*) -fruit;
- blackcurrant (*Ribes nigrum*) -leaves;
- bitter cucumber (*Momordica charantia*) –leaves and shoots;
- aloe (*Aloe arborescens*) -leaves.

Enzymatic analysis performed:

Hydrolytic (digestive) enzymes: lipase, amylase, protease and some oxido-reductive enzymes.[20-23] These analyzes were performed for the four plants, like raw material, as a potential enzyme sources.

Methods:

Considering that have followed the main enzymes involved in the digestion process specific methods were used to determine the digestive hydrolytic enzymes: amylase, protease, lypase. The methods used are:

-*Amylase* was determined according to the method of α -amylase dosage (Hostettler method).

Principle of the method: Starch is hydrolyzed, under the catalytic action of α -amylase fragments reductive group, which can be determined by the 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid. Nitro-aminosalicylic acid concentration formed is measured colorimetrically corresponding to enzymatic activity. A unit consists of one micromole of reducing groups (calculated maltose equivalents) per minute at 37°C.

-*Protease* is dosed according to the classical method of endoproteinase dosing (Drapeau method). This method consists in the determination of enzymatic activity in the cleavage of casein used as a substrate. One unit is the amount of enzyme which liberates acid soluble fragments measured colorimetrically corresponding to enzyme activity (at wavelength 280 nm) per minute at 37°C and pH 7.8.

-*Lypase* is fatty acids dosed method (Willstatter method). resulting from the hydrolysis of triglycerides from olive oil used as a substrate in the presence of lipase extracted and assayed titrimetrically with an alcoholic organic solution solvent of hydroxide in the presence of phenolphthalein - as an indicator. A lipolytic unit is defined as the amount of enzyme which, under the reaction conditions, issued 1 μ mol fatty acid per minute at 37°C.

3. Results and Discussion

Selected plants were studied and found to be rich in digestive enzymes, as follows:

- The highest amylase levels in descending order are at: - bitter cucumber => blackcurrant => buckthorn => aloe;

Lipase recorded the highest values on:

- buckthorn => aloe => blackcurrant => bitter cucumber;

The highest values of protease were determined at: - aloe => bitter cucumber => buckthorn => black currant.

Fig 1. Amylase levels in plant material analyzed

Fig 2. Lipase levels in plant material analyzed

Fig 3. Protease levels in plant material analyzed

There have been studied on digestive enzyme content of the four main herbs that are widely used and appreciated in modern phytotherapy: Buckthorn, Momordica, Aloe and Blackberry. The results showed that besides of phytochemical rich complex of these herbs that contain digestive interest enzymes to regulate digestive processes.

Conclusions

The authors of this study have been studied a variety of plant materials with an increased enzymatic potential in synergy with existing active substances from plants which supplement the body needs, to develop natural enzyme dietary supplements, so:

-Buckthorn fruit has a higher content in lipase and amylase in comparison to the other plant material studied.

- Momordica has higher content of amylase and protease and lipase to the most increased in the group of plants investigated. *M. charantia* has significant antidiabetic as well as hypolipidemic activity so that it can be used as an adjuvant along with allopathic treatment of medicine to

treat diabetes as well as to delay the late complications of diabetes.

- Blackcurrant has low-protease and lipase content beside of the Momordica fruit, and rich in amylase, compared with Aloe and Buckthorn.

-Aloe -leaves are rich in protease and have a lower content of lipase and amylase in correlation to studied plant material.

-On that basis of studies and results can range phytotherapeutic properties of these plants and the benefits of digestive processes can also be used in combination for development of preparations rich in digestive enzymes.

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THE CHARACTERIZATION OF ROMANIAN VEGETABLE OILS AND OIL EXTRACTS BY ADVANCED TECHNIQUES

N. IONESCU (BORDEI)*, M. POPESCU* , V. TAMAS**

Abstract: *The paper highlights the importance of active compounds from some cold-press vegetable oils. These cold press vegetable oils comes from the seeds of organic -grown plants such us: hemp, safflower, milk thistle, black cumin, sea buckthorn, and oily extract from carrot. To emphasizing the essential fatty acids in these oils has been used the technique of gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and the study of carotenoid composition in carrott extracts (in selected oils) was performed by molecular absorption spectrophotometry UV-VIS and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).*

Oily extracts obtained will be used for the synthesis of nanostructured lipid carriers (NLC) in order to be used in cosmetic formulations with acne role.

Keywords: *vegetable oils, oily extracts, GC-MS, HPLC, UV-VIS*

1. Introduction

Herbs are inexhaustible sources of raw materials for the food, pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries. The cultivation and exploitation of medicinal plants as precursors of bioactive vegetable oils and extracts in organic farming system represent an alternative to the conventional production methods, being accompanied by several advantages: promote environmentally friendly technology by excluding synthetic chemicals, provide healthy agricultural products, and ensure a clean environment, conserves natural resources.

For the production of vegetable oils rich in unsaturated fatty acids such as: ω -3, ω -6 and ω -9 were used seeds and fruit of carefully selected plant material (eg. hemp, milk thistle, safflower, black cumin seeds and sea buckthorn fruits). Production of various plant sources by cold pressing is the technology that separates the liquid component (oil) from a mixture solid - liquid.

Obtained from certain species approved of *Cannabis sativa*, hemp oil is rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids and it's used for its cholesterol-lowering properties, in treating skin diseases and hemp seeds are considered as an interesting nutrient source.

The Milk Thistle oil containing unsaturated fatty acids especially linoleic and oleic acids, many sterols, vitamin E (alpha-tocopherol) and an outstanding antioxidant activity.

Safflower oil containing a large amount of polyunsaturated fatty acids up to 80% (linoleic acid conjugated), helps to lower oxidative stress of the cells, preserves the integrity of cell membranes, it is useful for treatment of skin disorders (acne, cuperosis) and stimulates the collagen production.

Like the other vegetable oils, the Black Cumin oil rich in essential fatty acids, improves the skin condition and the immunity system.

The cold press oil from Sea Buckthorn fruits is rich in carotenoids and particular is the content of some essential fatty acids especially palmitoleic acid.

These vegetable oils will be used to obtain oil extracts rich in carotenoids and subsequently used in cosmetic formulations acting anti acne.

2. Materials and Methods

The selected vegetable oils were obtained by cold pressing of the plant seeds from hemp, safflower, milk thistle, black cumin, including sea buckthorn fruits grown on organic soils.

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The carrot oily extract were obtained by cold maceration in the absence of light for 7 days, from carrot root powder in selected oils.

The identification and characterization of fatty acids was performed by gas chromatography technique coupled with mass spectrometry (GC-MS), after derivatization to the methyl esters by transesterification of oil triglycerides through alkali-catalyzed methanolysis using a gas chromatograph Termo – GC with DSQ P 5000 detector. The column used was Macrogol 2000, $\Phi = 0.25$ mm, $l = 30$ m, He gas flow = 1 mL/min, injection temperature = 25°C, column temperature = 250°C. To identify the peaks the NIST spectra library has been used.

The concentration of carotens from the *oily carrot extracts* has been determined using Jasco UV-VIS absorption spectrometer at $\lambda = 460$ nm with 10 mm cuves.

In order to perform measurements of carotenoids by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). The oily carrot extracts were treated with benzene and 2-propanol, centrifuged at 3000 rot/min for 30 minutes, then filtered through a 0.22 mm filter. It was used a Dionex HPLC (P 540 pump equipped with four elements and capabilities for the gradient). Detection was performed with a UV detector at a wavelength of 450 nm.

Fig. 1. Chromatograms GC-MS to studied vegetable oils

3. Results and discussion

Identification and determination of saponifiable (fatty acids) compounds with GC-MS

The vegetable oil show a complex formula, mainly containing saponifiable compounds (eg.: mono-, di- and triacylglycerols containing

saturated and unsaturated fatty acids ~98% and in a small ratio free fatty acids) but also, other natural compounds- unsaponifiable derivatives- carotenoids and other pigments, tocopherols, waxes, sterols, phospholipids.

The chromatographic profile of the fatty acids from the selected vegetable oils are in the chromatograms from figure.1 and their content in the table 1.

Table 1. The fatty acids content of vegetable oils

No.	Name	Fatty acids content [%]					
		Oleic acid (Omega 9)	Linoleic acid (Omega 6)	Linolenic acid (Omega 3)	Other fatty acids		
					Palmitic acid	Stearic acid	Palmitoleic acid
1	Hemp oil	21.9	51.2	16.8	8.9	4.5	-
2	Milk Thistle oil	29.2	44.4	4.1	14.4	8.0	-
3	Safflower oil	11.6	77.6	0.2	7.8	2.8	-
4	Black Cumin oil	24.9	52.0	0.5	17.3	5.3	-
5	Sea Buckthorn oil	20.9	5.7	2.9	35.5	1.2	25.4

Analyzing oil composition determined by GC-MS, it can be seen that the richest oil in omega-6, is safflower oil with > 77% linoleic acid, and the smallest amount of linoleic acid was found in sea buckthorn oil (~6%). A content in oleic acid (omega-9) of between 20 to 30% was determined for milk thistle, black cumin, hemp and sea buckthorn oils.

Regarding linolenic acid (omega-3) shows a higher composition thereof in hemp oil (~17%), milk thistle (~4%), sea buckthorn oil (~3%), the rest of vegetable oils (safflower and black cumin) presenting a much lower omega-3 fatty acid (<1%).

Hemp shows an ideal ratio of approximately 3: 1 omega-6 to omega-3.

The highest content of saturated fatty acids, meaning *palmitic acid* is found in sea buckthorn fruit oil (~35%), black cumin oil (> 17%), and the *stearic acid* was found in milk thistle oil (~8%). The presence of palmitoleic acid in the sea buckthorn oil (~25%) is mandatory.

Identification and determination of non-saponifiable actives – Carotens

The concentration of carotens from the *oily carrot extracts* has been determined using UV-VIS absorption spectrometer and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).

The total carotenoids content expressed in β -carotene from the carrot oily extracts is in the figure 2.

Fig. 2. The total carotenoids content expressed in β -carotene

The largest amount of β -carotene is found in carrot oily extract, in sea buckthorn oil (350 mg / 100 g), the other oily extracts having a similar composition.

HPLC chromatograms shown in figures 3 and 4 illustrate the presence of oily carotenoid extracts studied.

Fig. 3. HPLC chromatogram for the oily carrot extract (identical) in hemp, safflower, milk thistle and black cumin oil

Fig. 4. HPLC Chromatogram for oily carrot extract in sea buckthorn oil

A comparison of the chromatograms obtained on oily extracts of vegetable materials studied revealed that the carrot extract in *hemp, safflower, milk thistle and black cumin oil* presents a high content of β -carotene while those in *sea buckthorn oil* presents also significant amounts of lutein and vitamins such as retinol and tocopherol.

Conclusions

A set of suitable analyses methods like gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and ^1H -RMN have been employed in order to establish the profile of unsaturated and polyunsaturated fatty acids (eg.: *linoleic acid, linolenic acid, oleic acid, palmitic acid,*

palmitoleic acid and total carotenoids expressed in β -caroten). There was a good agreement between quantitative results obtained by GC-MS and H-RMN techniques.

The rich content of *Linolenic acid, ω -3 and Linoleic acid, ω -6* detected in the five selected oils from the study (e.g. 78% ω -6 in *Safflower oil*, 54% ω -6 in *Hemp oil* 52% ω -6 in *Black Cumin oil*, 44% ω -3 in *thistle oil*, 35% *Palmitic acid and 25% Palmitoleic acid in Sea Buckthorn oil*) represents a promising approach for the development of new classes of lipid nanotransporters containing natural plant compounds of high interest, in order to obtain acting anti-acne cosmetic formulations.

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INTRODUCTION AND PROMOTING CONDIMENTAR-AROMATIC SPECIES VERBENA TRIPHILLA L'Her. IN THE CLIMATIC CONDITIONS OF REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

L. CHISNICEAN

Abstract: *Verbena triphylla* L'Her is the species that possess unique chemical composition due-curative, flavoring, decorative, being widely used in sundries domain. Practical diversity was our landmark studies of introduction in the climatic conditions of our country. Since the volume of the original material that we had was small, I began research for defining methods of reproduction of the species. Within two years were identified cheap and most effective methods being chosen as asexual multiplication - potting-up. The method allows for a considerable amount of rooted plants, as well as raw materials resulting from mature plants.

Keywords: *Verbena*, spice, method, multiplication, rooting, cuttings, substrate, stimulator

1. Introduction

Verbena triphylla L'Hér. is a perspective perennial species with spice, aromatic, curative, proprieties and decorative appearance. The main chemical components of lemon verbena oil are borneol, geraniol, linalool, nerol, citral, dipentene, limonene and myrcene [1]. The therapeutic properties of lemon verbena oil are anti-oxidant [2], anti-Candida [3], anti-septic, anti-spasmodic, aphrodisiac, digestive, emollient, febrifuge, hepatic, insecticide, sedative, stomachic and tonic.

Verminoside and verbascoside are natural compounds present in plants used in traditional medicine. They exhibit several biological activities including anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial and anti-tumor properties[4] In the digestive system, lemon verbena oil helps with cramps, indigestion and liver congestion and is helpful to restore the liver after a binge and when suffering from a hangover.

The stimulant action on the digestive system helps to digest fats and the excellent action on the liver helps in cases of cirrhosis, as well as alcoholism. It soothes the respiratory tract and calms heart palpitations. Lemon verbena oil helps to banish depression and relaxes as well as refreshes the body and mind, while uplifting the spirits and promoting stress control.

Leaves and flowers are used for culinary purposes (teas, desserts, fruit salads and jams) for perfumes and cosmetics. It can also be used to brighten the taste of fish, poultry, veggie marinades, stuffing, salad dressing, jellies, and vinegar.

2. Material and methods

Its introduction in the climate conditions of Moldova is related especially by the choice a method of multiplication.

The experiments regarding propagation methods were carried out during 2013-2014 period. During the process of introduction there have been applied several methods of vegetative multiplication in order to identify the most efficient and fast one.

Propagation by cuttings is the most common method of plant multiplication and is based on attributes that have some species to reconstruct new plant by organs or parts of organs, when detached from the mother plant and are placed in the environment conditions.

Different kinds of cuttings were sampled for rooting. After the nature of tops, shoot and stem tops were used, and by tissue consistency were collected - herbaceous cuttings, taken from soft green stems and lignified ones. The period of collecting the cuttings a varied - during summer-autumn and early spring.

The method was supplemented with rhyzogene substances (hormones) treatments to stimulate rooting. River sand, and mixture forest soil and Biohumus served as a substrate for rooting. Purification of the collected material and of the tool used in the cuttings process was made using solution - 1% - solution Potassium permanganate.

The cutting sampled in spring were planted in mini-greenhouses covered with special

material "Agril" and those sampled in summer-autumn - in containers. Sampling of cuttings was performed with horticultural scissors and shaping for rooting - with a sharp scalpel. The lots of apical after tissue consistency were erbaceous and semilignified, those from branches - semilignified and strains - lignified.

In winter the plants of *Verbena triphylla* L'Her lose foliage and cuttings sampled early spring are without leaves. Before collecting cuttings mother- plants were fertilized and well irrigated.

The cuttings collected in the summer-autumn period were shaped by removing two pairs of basal leaves and the other being halved. The cuts should be straight, without chipping. Here and there are made small incisions superficial tissue for stimulating the roots.

The cuttings intended for rooting group were 8-10cm long and were half incorporated into the substrate. Before incorporation, the cuttings were cut off below the basal node, one part being processed with rhizogene stimulator and the other remaining raw.

Green seedlings were incorporated vertically and the semilignified and lignified ones - at an angle of 15 degrees. After incorporation, the substrate around seedlings was irrigated and well

Fig. 1. Apical rooting cuttings

It was time to perform transplantation in larger containers and permanent place of growth for further development (fig.1, 2). The operation was carried out with great care, because newly formed roots are very fragile.

For transplanted cuttings were created semidarkness conditions. The rooting rate of green apical cuttings treated with rooting stimulator was of 69% while the rooting rate 67% of the untreated ones was of 67% being insignificant, given the cost of preparation. Apical cuttings green leaves often touching the

compacted, this enhanced rooting. In both cases the light was intense but filtered.

3. Results and discussions

Factors that intervene in the production capacity of roots were identified as a result of the research. One of the important factors was the age mother plant. When mother plants were younger the propagation capacity is greater. The mother plant nutrition important was also important; root cuttings formed much faster and were qualitative.

Light had an active role in the success of cuttings but this role is difficult to quantify, long days favored for rooting. One of the key factors that influenced directly rooting was constant humidity; both the substrate and the air influenced rooted cuttings.

Throughout cuttings was carefully controlled evaporation and water absorption from the ground. If the substrate (sand or mixture) is dry, cuttings will wither, if it is too wet, they will rot.

Over 12 to 15 days, buds appeared on the small stem of the cuttings, which began to develop intensively. This is the stage when the cuttings have already formed root.

Fig. 2. Apical semilignified cuttings

substrate causing rot infection and their low rate of rooting. Semilignified apical cuttings had the highest rate of rooting.

Those treated with rooting stimulator - 89%, and the unprocessed ones -79% (tab.1). Lignified cuttings derived from branches and strain had the same average rate of rooting: 70-75% rooting. I also noticed that rooting substrate isn't the most important criterion in the rooting process, since the results were similar (66% rooting by stimulating both the substrate and on sand, and 65% unprocessed both substrates).

Table 1. Rate of rooting different types of cuttings and rooting substrate

Types of cuttings	The rate of rooting, %			
	Sand substrate		Substrate mixture	
	Processed by rooting stimulate	Raw	Processed by rooting stimulate	Raw
Apical green	69	67	68	66
Apical semilignified	89	79	88	82
Lignified of the branches	73	70	74	71
Lignified of the de strains	75	74	75	75

Lignified cuttings derived from branches and strain had the same average rate of 70-75% rooting. The cuttings processed with rooting stimulator had a better rate of rooting, the results being similar on both substrates (Fig.3).

For the success of the cuttings, the sampling period was important. Mature plants of *Verbena triphylla* L'Her during the cold period are kept in the greenhouse at a temperature of 10-12⁰C.

Fig.3. Influence on rooting cuttings origin

Apical cuttings taken from them are the early spring, without foliage, but good rooting.

The summer - autumn apical cuttings, have 4-5 pairs of leaves, are green but semilignified. Their rooting rate is also pretty good 89% in early spring cuttings and 85% in summer - autumn (fig.3). Lignified cuttings, collected so early as spring and summer - autumn had lower rates of 78-81% rooting. Rooting is influenced largely by stimulating rhizogene processing.

Conclusions

Multiplying this precious species spicy, aromatic and medicinal should be performed using apical cuttings semilignificați.

Applying rooting stimulators allows rapid rooting without massive loss of materil. Collecting material is more rational multiplication during early spring.

The pressing needs, pote multiplication material collected and in summer - autumn. Rooting substrate that is not directly influenceon this process.

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ETHNOBOTANICAL AND ECOLOGICAL STUDIES OF WILD EDIBLE PLANTS FROM BUGEAC STEPPE, REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

CIOCARLAN N.¹, GHENDOV V.

Abstract: A study on the traditional use of wild edible plants in three settlements (Bugeac, Dezghingea and Topal, district Comrat), from the Bugeac steppe region, located in the southern part of the Republic of Moldova was carried out. Total 38 wild edible species from 33 genera and 17 families were identified. Data were obtained through ethnobotanical interviews with villagers in the investigated area. A total number of 17 people of different age were interviewed. The plants are presented in a table with Latin and common names, useful parts, ethno-medical uses and methods of consumption. Nine species are frequently collected and used by locals

Keywords: ethnobotany, bio-ecology, wild edible plants, Bugeac steppe;

1. Introduction

Data collection on traditional medicine, more recently, ethnobotanical studies are increasing in recent decades in many countries [1, 3, 7-12, 14-16, 18]. Gaining knowledge about native edible and medicinal plants used in folk medicine and for human consumption through ethnobotanical studies requires reconsideration of their pharmacological action and nutritive value for the better use. Also, the information directly contributes to the conservation and sustainable use of their resources.

In our republic ethnobotanical studies show a relatively new research direction [5], but perspective as local flora provides us a large number of plants with important edible and therapeutic qualities, some growing wild in abundance, requiring no cultivation investment. Little information and documented references [2] on the ethnobotany of edible and medicinal plants spontaneously growing in the flora of Republic of Moldova are available withal.

This study was aimed to identify and document the wild edible plants and their traditional uses by three local communities in the Bugeac steppe region, located in the southern part of the Republic of Moldova.

2. Methods

Study area

Using both ethnobotanical and ecological methods, the study was carried out in three rural

settlements from district Comrat: vill. Bugeac (N 46° 24' 23", E 28° 42' 48"), vill. Dezghingea (N 46° 25' 13", E 28° 37' 24") and vill. Topal (N 46° 27' 35", E 28° 40' 23").

These localities are situated in the northern part of Bugeac steppe region, characterized generally as steppes of the plains, plateau and hills of the western Black Sea, west of the Dniester with the main habitat type being Ponto-Sarmatic steppes.

Data collection

Ethnobotanical information was accumulated via informed questionnaires and interviews with local people during the 2012-2014 periods. A total number of 17 people of different age were interviewed. Additionally, to enrich understanding about different species of edible plants growing spontaneously in the studied area oral informal discussions with key informants was carried out. Traditional knowledge related to the collection and methods of use of wild edible species was documented.

Identification of the plant samples

Collected plant samples were pressed according to standard guides. At the next stage, samples were stick to the herbarium cardboards and taxonomically identified using the up to date scientific works [4, 6, 13, 19]. Labelled voucher specimens are deposited in the Herbarium of the Botanical Garden (Institute) of Academy of Sciences of Moldova.

¹Botanical Garden (Institute) of Academy of Science of Moldova

3. Results and discussions

Use A total of 38 species from 33 genera and 17 families that have been traditionally consumed in the study area were documented. They account 5,3% of the 715 species registered in the Bugeac steppe

region, located in the southern part of the Republic of Moldova [17].

Recorded data are presented by list of species with scientific and local name, family, plant parts used and method of consumption (Table 1).

Table 1. Wild edible plants traditionally used as food in the study area

Nr	Botanical name/ local name	Family	Part used	Methods of consumption
1	<i>Allium sphaerocephalon</i> L. / ceapă	Alliaceae	leaves, bulbs	raw, salad, boiled, soup
2	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i> L./ știr	Amaranthaceae	leaves, seeds	raw, boiled, soup, maize meal
3	<i>Asparagus officinalis</i> L./ sparanghel	Asparagaceae	young shoots	raw, cooked, soup, sauces
4	<i>Cichorium inthybus</i> L. / cicoare	Asteraceae	leaves, root	raw, cooked, soup, sauces
5	<i>Arctium lappa</i> L. / brusture	Asteraceae	young leaves, root	raw, cooked for diabetics
6	<i>Scorzonera hispanica</i> L./ lăptiuță	Asteraceae	leaves, roots	raw in salad, cooked, soup
7	<i>Taraxacum officinalis</i> Wigg./ păpădie	Asteraceae	leaves, root, flower	steamed, preserved in vinegar
8	<i>Artemisia absinthium</i> L. / pelin	Asteraceae	young leaves	wormwood wine, condiment
9	<i>Bunias orientalis</i> L. / brăbin	Brassicaceae	leaves, young stem	cooked as vegetable
10	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i> (L.) Medik / traista ciobanului	Brassicaceae	leaves, seedpods, seeds	raw, salads, condiment, seeds ground and used in soup
11	<i>Lepidium latifolium</i> L. / scvamăriț ă	Brassicaceae	leaves, seeds, roots	raw, salad, sauce, condiment
12	<i>Atriplex hortensis</i> L. / lobodă	Chenopodiaceae	leaves, seeds	raw, soup, bread baking
13	<i>Atriplex patula</i> L. / lobodă	Chenopodiaceae	leaves, seeds	cornmeal, sausages, roast lamb
14	<i>Chenopodium album</i> L. / tĂmăiț ă	Chenopodiaceae	leaves	raw or steamed, been dishes
15	<i>Chenopodium foliosum</i> Aschers / lobodă	Chenopodiaceae	leaves, seeds	cooked, rice dishes, read baking
16	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> L. / iarbă dulce	Fabaceae	roots	flavouring sweets, baked goods
17	<i>Berberis vulgaris</i> L. / dracilă	Berberidaceae	fruits	raw, cooked, jelly, jam, juice
18	<i>Lathyrus tuberosus</i> L. / limba cucului	Fabaceae	roots	baked like sweet potato
19	<i>Medicago sativa</i> L. / lucernă	Fabaceae	leaves, seeds	tea, salad, soup
20	<i>Trifolium pratense</i> L. / trifoi	Fabaceae	young leaves	raw, salad, boiled as vegetable
21	<i>Origanum vulgare</i> L. /sovărv	Lamiaceae	leaves, flowers	condiment, salad dressing, tea
22	<i>Thymus marschallianus</i> Willd./ cimbru	Lamiaceae	leaves, flowers	condiment, tea, salad
23	<i>Linum perenne</i> L. / ineaț ă	Linaceae	seeds	cooked as a flavouring, oil
24	<i>Lavatera thuringiaca</i> L. /nalbă	Malvaceae	young leaves	raw or cooked
25	<i>Malva neglecta</i> Wallr. / colăcei	Malvaceae	young shoots	raw, salad, cooked like lettuce
26	<i>Malva pusilla</i> Smith / colăcei mărunți	Malvaceae	young fruits	raw
27	<i>Malva sylvestris</i> L. / colăcei	Malvaceae	leaves	salad, soup
28	<i>Oenothera biennis</i> L. / luminița nopții	Onagraceae	fleshy roots, seeds	boiled, steamed, oil
29	<i>Phragmites australis</i> (Cav.) Trin.ex Steud. / trestie	Poaceae	young shoots, seeds	ground for making dumplings, ground and used as a flour
30	<i>Rumex acetosella</i> L. / măcriș	Polygonaceae	leaves	raw, green salad, cooked, soup
31	<i>Crataegus monogyna</i> Jacq. / păducel	Rosaceae	fruits, leaves	raw, jam, tea, dried for later use
32	<i>Fragaria viridis</i> (Duch.) Weston / fragi	Rosaceae	fruits	raw or cooked
33	<i>Geum urbanum</i> L. / cerențel	Rosaceae	leaves	cooked, soup, condiment
34	<i>Cerasus fruticosa</i> Pall. / cireș	Rosaceae	fruits	raw, dried for later use, tea
35	<i>Prunus spinosa</i> L. / porumbar	Rosaceae	fruits	raw, jellies, syrup, liqueur
36	<i>Rosa canina</i> L. / măceș	Rosaceae	fruits	raw, jam, syrup, tea
37	<i>Galium verum</i> L. / sĂnzienne	Rubiaceae	flowering stems	food colouring
38	<i>Urtica dioica</i> L. / urzicĂ	Urticaceae	leaves	nettle soup, purée

The most utilized species belong to *Rosaceae* (6 sp.), *Asteraceae* (5 sp.), *Fabaceae*, *Chenopodiaceae* and *Malvaceae*

with 4 species each, that represent more than 60% of registered species. Three species are members of *Brassicaceae* family and the

remaining families (*Alliaceae*, *Amarathaceae*, *Asparagaceae*, *Berberidaceae*, *Lamiaceae*, *Linaceae*, *Onagraceae*, *Poaceae*, *Polygonaceae*, *Rubiaceae* and *Urticaceae*) are represented by one or two species each. Herbs and shrubs make up the highest proportion of the registered edible species.

At the present time, less than 30% of recorded species are used by local people, while another more than 70% have been frequently consumed in the past, but not anymore. A good numbers of species (*Phragmites australis*, *Amaranthus retroflexus*, *Bunias orientalis*, *Trifolium pratense*, *Lathyrus tuberosus*, *Malva neglecta*, *Atriplex hortensis*, *Lepidium latifolium* etc.) were

mentioned by respondents as plants consumed during famine (in XX century, after the 2nd World War) and no longer used today. Less of the traditional knowledge has been lost in the case of wild edible fruits.

Young shoots, leaves and fruits are the plant parts used commonly by local people in the area. One of the most representative edible plant in this region is the nettle (*Urtica dioica*), which is used widely even nowadays. It is a very popular vegetable being an indispensable component in a variety of recipes. The most frequent is “*tocana de urzici*” (fig 1.), made from quick-boiled young leaves mixed with stewed onions and flour. Another common use of the plant in the area is nettle soup.

Fig. 1. "Tocana de urzici" prepared with young leaves of *Urtica dioica*

The species used for fruits (*Rosa canina*, *Prunus spinosa*, *Berberis vulgaris*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Fragaria viridis*) continue to be collected and traditionally used. Most of them belong to the *Rosaceae* family. The most commonly collected wild fruit species remain to be *P. spinosa*, followed by *R. canina*. The fruits of *P. spinosa*, called “*porumbrele*” are consumed directly in the field after the first frosts, when they became overripe. A home-made alcoholic drink with *P. spinosa* fruits is an up-to-date tradition in the area. It is also used as medicinal remedy in the treatment of diarrhoea. The fruits

of *R. canina* and *C. monogyna* are harvested, dried and used mainly for their therapeutic properties as a tea.

Other important species used as wild vegetables are *Rumex acetosella*, *Origanum vulgare*, *Malva pusilla*, *Taraxacum officinale*. The most common method of consumption are fresh, added to salads, or cooked by boiling and steaming of young leaves or young shoots as part of various recipes for soups, sauces, dumplings etc. A delicious young shoots and leaves of *R. acetosella* are eaten raw in the spring. They are also an excellent addition to salads and soups,

called in the area “*supă verde*”. The immature fruits of *Malva pusilla* are collected and immediately consumed by children. The most commonly used herbs such *R. acetosella* and *O.*

vulgare are taken out from their natural habitat and transferred in home gardens to be cultivated for home consumption or even for commercial purposes.

Fig. 2. Wild fruit species used in the area (*P. spinosa*, *R. canina*, *B. vulgaris*, *C. monogyna*)

The aromatic plants *Origanum vulgare* and *Thymus marschallianus* are used as culinary and food flavouring plants due to the presence of essential oil. These species are largely prepared as herbal teas and used in the treatment of various affections related to respiratory and digestive systems. Many other species (*Cichorium inthybus*, *Arctium lappa*, *Taraxacum officinalis*, *Artemisia absinthium*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, *Oenothera biennis*, *Prunus spinosa*, *Rosa canina*, *Urtica dioica*, *Capsela bursa-pastoris*, *Berberis vulgaris*, *Geum*

urbanum, *Urtica dioica*) have been mentioned to possess curative effects, being traditionally used for treating many diseases.

Some species represent the indispensable part of ritual food or drink for religious holidays. An example of this is the traditional drink “*vin cu pelin*” obtained by maceration of wormwood young leaves in home-made red wine. It is consumed in spring at religious holidays “*Rusalii*” and “*St. Marina*” as a symbol of health and blood purification.

Fig. 3. Species used for food flavouring and as vegetables (*Th. marschallianus*, *T. officinalis*, *O. vulgare*)

The ecological studies reveal that according to ecomorphs, the most numerous group is hemichriptophytes with 18 species that represent 47,3% of registered taxa. The absolute predominance of the hemichriptophytes indicates

a climate with a hydric deficit in the area. Therophytes are represented by 11 species (28,9%), followed by phanerophytes with 5 species (13,2%), geophytes and chamephytes with 2 species (5,3%) each (fig. 4).

From a phytogeographic point of view (geoelements), it is noticed that most of the species belong to the Mediterranean geoelement (36,8%), followed by Eurasiatic (31,6%), circumpolar (13,2%), adventive and European with a share of 7,9% each. Less in number (2,6%) are cosmopolite species (fig. 5). The

distribution of the species according to humidity show a large presence of xeromesophytes, comprising 20 species (52,7%), followed by mesophytes represented by 16 species (42,1%), mesohygrophytes and xerophytes with 1 species (2,6%) each (fig. 6).

Fig. 4. Ecomorphs of wild edible plants

Fig. 5. Distribution of geoelements

Fig. 6. Spectrum of bioforms

Conclusions

Taxonomic diversity of the flora of the studied area is reach and provides diverse valuable plants. Most of the mentioned species are popular among the communities of studied area being potentially a good source of edible and medicinal plants.

The result of the study reveals that people from investigated area possess a good knowledge on the wild edible plants growing around their villages. At the present time, less than 30% of recorded species are used by local people, while another more than 70% have been frequently consumed in the past, but not anymore. A good

numbers of species were mentioned by respondents as plants consumed during famine and no longer used today.

That demonstrate that they continue to use the knowledge of wild medicinal crop in their day-to-day life, but the tradition of their using is obviously declining. That fact encourages further ethnobotanical investigations in rural areas not only in this region but also throughout the country.

Assuredly, the harmonious connection of this traditional knowledge with modern science is basic in order to promote conservation and sustainable use of these indigenous edible plants.

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ELEMENTS OF MOUNTAIN BIOECONOMICS IN THE PERMACULTURE CONCEPT, WITH APPLICATIONS IN CARPATHIANS

R. GRUIA¹

Abstract: Under the large Bioeconomy frame, the paper proposes to find basic elements and afferent solutions for the dynamic equilibrium of mountainous landscape. in the idea of increasing the attractiveness of mountain areas. The paper describes the bio solutions in mountainous areas where there are been less approached aspects linked to inaccessible and extremely unfavorable zones. With the help of the modulisation theory and the methodology of integronic dynamics, the study describes the application of the permaculture concept for these extremely fragile zones, in order to bring them to ecosystem production stage and to install life by trophic chains specific to steep and rocky coasts. There is elaborated a technological model in the context of the presentation of permaculture concept, of the principles, basic rules, as well as of specific techniques (terraces, ponds, raised strata and others). In order to exemplify, there is presented a case study. There are elaborated a series of solutions to adapt the permaculture concept to the specific conditions of the Romanian Carpathian Mountains.

Keywords: bioeconomy, landscape, mountain ecosystem, montanology, permaculture.

1. Introduction

The integronic management in mountain modules applies through understanding *production modules* as complex systems producing food in agroecosystems or in „mini-ecosystems” of controlled environment and space, when in the mountain environment appear major modifications consequently to climate, economic and social changes. Such an integration in the large frame of bioeconomy, makes nothing but sustain, through complementarities, the conceptual transition in the mountain zone, from the principles of Green Economy (non polluting, natural etc) towards the application of the principles of Blue Economy, i.e. circular economy, with eco-social impact (especially by price reduction), passing from the *economy based on product* to *economy based on system*.

The economy based on contemporary biologic revolution, i.e. **bioeconomy** or **biotechnomy** (Biobased economy, bioeconomy or biotechnomy) refers to all economic activities derived from scientific and research activity

focused on biotechnology. In other words, it is based on the understanding of mechanisms and processes at genetic and molecular level and their application at industrial processes or even at geographic scenery [Martinez,R., Enríquez, J., West, J. ,2003]. Therefore, the evolution of the biotechnology industry and its application at industries from agriculture, at chemical or energy ones, as well as at the health field constitutes the classic example of bioeconomic activity [Smyth, S. J., and col., 2011; [Wesseler, J., and col., 2011](#)].

In the National Bioeconomy plans (as, for example, in „[White House Promotes a Bioeconomy](#)”, April 26, 2012) there is discussed a series of measures and strategies to stimulate the research and development of agro-zoo-technical, biofuel cultures and production, and processes of biologic fabrication, of medical treatments, that might replace tough industrial methods.

By extrapolation, from the perspective of *sustainable development of territorial scenery*, the application of the principles of bioeconomy harmonizes with the *multiple integration* of the ecosystem components, from molecular level to the level of the individual and of the community. We are referring to their structure and

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functionality, in function of their specificity. What interests here are **mountain ecosystems** and the methods through which there may be achieved bioeconomical models.

The present paper has as an objective such a model, starting from the Modulisation Theory and the Integrative Management [Gruia, R., 2011, 2013], from the program of mountain development in the Romanian Carpathians [Rey, R., Gruia, R., 2013] and from the agro-food bioeconomy strategy from Romania [Bogdan, A.T., Gruia, R., Toba G.F., Pasalau Carmen, 2014].

From our observations, the systemic evolution may be achieved by landscape modulization of the mountain zones, taking into account the following principles: (a) the mountain systems are open, dynamic and complex, with a tendency towards disequilibrium, as a condition for development; (b) open systems exchange Energy, Substance or Information with their environment and, when pushed „far-from-equilibrium” create new structures and a new order.

The modulization process or eco-modulization, by the *concept of emergent integratics* and, respectively, by the *principle of eco-emergent integration* [Gruia, R., 2009, 2011], approaches the flows of Substance, Energy and Information that sweep mountain systems from the perspective of eco-energetic analyses, of cogeneration and eMergetic sustainability.

2. Work Method

For the mountain zone, *the technological model of integrative modulization* is based

on systemic integration [Gruia, R., 2009], which presupposes entrance and process of *Substance, Energy and Information* (the 3 aspects of the same *Fundamental existence*) *together* determined in modular dynamics, syncretic and synchronic, with synergic effect, having as a result emergence at a new level of a superior order .

From all types of production modules, the technical & I.T. application first of all interests for **mountain agro-modules**. This fact methodologically implies a series of reference elements necessary to the adaptation of the had in mind modules, for different specific situations of a fragile zone, as the mountain one is: - to be energetically autonomous on Solar and Aeolian bases, - to be able to recycle rain and used water, - to transform waste and dejections in fertilizer manure, - to organize a culture rotation in order to allow soil to regenerate without fertilizers. Last but not least, there will be taken into account climate changes, plant exposition in relation to cardinal points, as well as soil and subsoil offer (ex. there may be arranged underground hothouses).

3. Results and Discussions

Without entering into details, we consider it useful to show the place and conceptual and applicative role of permaculture in the general frame of modular agriculture (table 1).

Table 1. *Modular Agriculture in Relation to Landscape*

Crt. nr.	APPLIED AGRICULTURAL CONCEPT	EFFECT UPON BIODIVERSITY	TYPE OF AGRICULTURE
1.	MONOCULTURE	Biodiversity impoverishment	- Modern agriculture (intensive, of high economic efficiency) in extravilan rural space / unicorporated territory in the locality - Peri-urban agriculture (industrial agriculture and animal breeding)
2.	POLICULTURE	Biodiversity enrichment	- Semi-subsistence agriculture - Sustainable mountain agriculture - Wet zone sustainable agriculture - Urban agriculture of the future – vertical farms
3.	PERMACULTURE	Permanent balanced biodiversity	- Fragile zone agriculture (inaccessible, wet, faraway mountain ones etc.)

From the wide range of the typology of agricultural systems, what interests in this paper is the **efficacy of mountain agri-modules**. Thus, we mention that beyond **economic efficacy**, in case of agri-modules, there is analyzed the **ecosystem efficacy**, by cumulus of the *environment work* (solar energy, bio-geo-chemical cycles, soil fertility, climate and meteorological contribution etc.), next to *human work* (as for example in mountain agroecosystems, mountain eco-farms, mountain agri-touristic systems, associative mountain platforms, production systems in space and controlled environment from the mountain zone, including arrangements based on the permaculture concept). We are referring to multiple integration which, at systemic level, also has connotation of alimentary integronics and even of mountain gastro-tourism [Gruia, R., 2014; Gruia, R., Bogdan, A.T., Rey, R., Tobă, G.F., 2015].

In this context we discern the *socio-economic perspective* which has as an objective to regenerate the mountain zone viability and attractiveness (it makes the object of other studies and researches), as well as the *techno-ecological perspective* which has as an objective the dynamic equilibrium of the mountain module on the principles of the Eco-emergent Integronics. In the second perspective, we refer to a consequence of multiple, synchronic and syncretic integrations, with synergic effect and emergent result, that creates the premises of the manifestation at a superior level of the mountain module of the **capacity to rebalance and modernize after nature model** of the ecosystemic components (forests, pastures, waters, agricultural fields, animal breeding, rural space etc.)

THE CONCEPT OF PERMACULTURE represents the system that imitates Nature, *structurally* based on ecosystems and *functionally* on natural cycles.

The notion has been introduced by the Australian ecologist Bill Mollison and by his student, David Holmgren, and, as an origin, it comes from the term of „*permanent agriculture*” (at which, subsequently, of course, have been added new meanings and dimensions), the

concept being developed since 1978 [Holzer, S., 2010].

Synthesizing, **mountain permaculture** operationally incorporates: - projection (creation of tracks, raised strata, aquatic gardens, ponds, ditches to deposit humus and microclimates); as well as fish breeding, - cultivation of aquatic plants, - animal breeding, - fruit cultivation, - maintenance of alpine pastures and cultivation of alpine and medicinal plants; there is also presented forest agriculture (integration of trees and bushes in agriculture), and, complementarily, even tourism is not excluded [Holzer, S., 2000, 2002].

The mentioned complexity imposes a clarification based on the complementarities of the fields of activity (fig.2) and, respectively, on multidisciplinary (fig.3).

When initiating a mountain permaculture system there will be taken into account a series of principles of the mountain permaculture (table 2), as well as certain recommendations.

As recommendation of principle there may be mentioned: - the establishment of objectives for the given mountain landscape; - the aspect (land direction of orientation), altitude and climate; - land evaluation (geologic conditions, soil characteristics, elevation, exposition, relief, draining basins, anterior utilization of the land etc.); - biologic and technical evaluation (fauna and existing plants, suitable agro-zootechnical techniques etc.); - human resource evaluation (professional education and formation in mountain activities; connection with elements of attractiveness of the mountain zone; personalized production – therefore it is necessary serious qualification for mountain permaculture).

The system of mountain permaculture, in function of the typology of the **permacultural landscape** of the Carpathian Mountains differ in relation to the *altitude gradient* : - at an average altitude (500-1600 m), characterized by the bioclimate beech and spruce floor from the *forest zone*; - at high altitude (1600-2500 m), characterized by the bio climate savin and alpine barren land floor from the *alpine zone* [Rey,R., Gruia, R., Rey,A., 2015], as it is shown in figure 4.

Fig. 2. Dynamics of rebalance of landscape through reference fields of mountain permaculture

Fig. 3. Multidisciplinarity of the mountain permaculture system, component of the montanology corresponding field

Table 2. Basic Principles of the Mountain Permaculture

No.PRINCIPLE	SPECIFICATION
Principle 1	• All elements from a system of mountain permaculture interact between them.
Principle 2	• Multifunctionality: every element fulfills several functions and every function is fulfilled by several elements; mountain permaculture uses energy practically and efficiently, works with renewable energy.
Principle 3	• Natural resources are used.
Principle 4	• Intensive systems are used only on restricted areas (as the case).
Principle 5	• There are formed and used natural cycles and processes (ex.: bio-geo-chemical cycles; trophic chain etc.)
Principle 6	• There are created structures at a small scale, but as productive as possible, based on diversity instead of monoculture.

Fig. 4. Pretability of permaculture in the Romanian Carpathians

Pragmatic principles and actions of Carpathian landscape, may be synthesized in mountain technique in permacultural system, table 3. specific to the characteristics of the

Table 3. Characteristics of the Carpathian Perm Cultural Scenery

Crt. nr.	ALTITUDE OF THE CARPATHIAN LANDSCAPE	PRINCIPLES AND PRAGMATIC ACTIONS OF MOUNTAIN TECHNIQUES IN PERMACULTURAL SYSTEM
1.	Permacultural landscape at average altitude (500-1600 m)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - easier to put in work a permacultural system at average altitude (as the land is relatively flat, sunny, less open to terrain slipping and to gap formation, i.e. erosion carved by a flush etc.); - it needs less energy; - in „unfavorable” locations it is aimed to compensate the little duration of the season, but also lower temperatures (here the climate changes could be favorable); - to avoid the negative wind effect, i.e. soil cooling and loss of humidity (it is indicates a wind curtain from fruit trees, forest fruit bushes, decorative bushes); - to avoid soil erosion on steep slopes by terraces and ditches of humus depositing, plantation of seeds in slope stone rifts and holes, or even on rock versant; - there may be made land remodeling with excavator; - livestock (pigs, hens, ducks etc.) play an integrative role in the permacultural system at average altitude. A well thought system of paddocks and enclosures allow keeping animals on the same land as plant cultures. Instead of destroying the land by over grazing, animals, in fact, help in applied technique.
2.	Permacultural landscape at high altitude (1600-2500 m) <i>PREMISES:</i> Floods, terrain slipping and destructions caused by tempest and snow are frequent at high altitude. Valuable biomass and fertile humus are lost.	<p><u>Plants oriented towards SOUTH</u> - cultivation fruit, vegetables, forest fruit – there are used sorts resistant at temperatures with large limits between day and night /soil is predisposed to drought (in summer), with plant drying / to avoid the lack of plants on southern slopes, in order to avoid erosion and the loss of sustenance substances from soil;</p> <p><u>Pants oriented towards NORTH</u> - being zones with only a few hours of solar light, it is important to choose sorts that ripen fast and that may completely ripen; in these conditions there are indicated raised strata;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - there will be made “natural batteries” for heat storage (example: there is dug a small lake or a pond in front of the stone niche where there are plants, for sun beam reflection).

WATER CIRCUIT AND TROPHIC CHAIN IN THE MOUNTAIN PERMACULTURAL SYSTEM makes from a functional point of view, the permacultural system redraws, after nature model, the water circuit and the trophic chain [Gruia,R., 2014].

Water, as it is known, is the fundament on which are based all forms of life. It is a very

precious resource, but, at the same time, much too abused and wasted nowadays. Nevertheless, ironically, we do not know to exploit its true potential. Especially in agriculture, where its role may much overdraw simple irrigations. About the sustainable manner in which we can use water, there may be observed the draft in figure 5.

Fig. 5. Presence of water flow in the permacultural landscape

The wet zones from the mountain module have a great importance because they constitute suitable environment for the creation of a **trophic chain**. There is observed a special specific for the trophic chains in function of altitude gradient, distinguishing thus: - trophic chains specific to the permacultural landscape at average altitude (500-1600 m); - trophic chains specific to permacultural landscape at high altitude (1600-2500 m).

In order to exemplify, we will refer to a mountain area which looks very much like many hill and mountain slopes from the Romanian Carpathians, both from climate point of view and configuration. We are referring to a mountain area of about 45 ha from Longau, Austria. Here, the well known farmer Sepp Holzer has been applying for over 50 years the permaculture methods. There are remarkably cultivated cereals, vegetables and fruit at altitudes even over 1500 meters. The success is due to plant cultivation in harmony with nature, producing bio, healthy cultures, without using chemicals, as in case of

monocultures. The used permaculture system has an enormous advantage: every year it naturally enriches the soil, the crops becoming more and more abundant. The result is charming, terraces scenery and interconnected ponds, which ensure everything that is necessary and, besides that, even a good income (fig. 6).

Creating micro climates and a series of terraces, raised layers and ponds, nature takes then care to offer humidity to all plants. More than that, for a maximal relation, the plants on families have been attentively chosen, facilitating thus the creation of more and more links between the elements of the system. For example, except the ponds, there are also built wet zones, slops, full of tree roots, sticks and stones, where water is smaller and warms very quickly. Here may quietly multiply larvae and saplings, not being stressed by raptors that swarm through deep ponds, connected to these wet zones. Because these stones and roots, being half in the water and half outside, behave like true thermal traps, transmitting sun heat to its ponds, it may be said

that this property has ponds with *central heating*, and all this for free ! [Holzer, S., 2010].

Marsh
arranged at
1400 m
altitude

(Kramenterhof,
Austria, Sepp
Holzer farm)

Fig. 6. Permacultural mountain landscape - system projected for the creation of the trophic chain

The roots prevent trout and pike to run and devour all the saplings. It creates thus a trophic chain, in which everybody has a chance – from the least larva, until saplings of 30 kilos, which swarm through the built ponds and enchant the clients from the zone. In such conditions fish are not bred with fodder, they naturally eat and, practically no one dies of hunger.

THE BUILDING OF MOUNTAIN TERRACES makes possible the valorization of

the non productive and inaccessible terrain. Thus one may also cultivate on very abrupt slopes, and there may also be used equipment even of medium size. By terraces there is achieved the inhibition to wash valuable humus (that without terraces is lost) and, at the same time, there is offered space to the zone for plants that may be bases for the creation of numerous micro climates (fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Diagram of principle of the land at the offset

The Kramterhof terraces spread from the valley (1100 m above sea level) up to the alpine pastures (1500 m altitude). Zones that couldn't be reached before are now accessible. In this way all the terrain may be efficiently used by projection in permacultural

project, with development of biodiversity for the equilibrium of the mountain module.

The construction of the mountain scenery is made in correlation with the **functions of strata and of terraces**. For instance, in the situation of

the existence of a railway which borders the land, or if there is a factory nearby, **raised strata** may be used, to keep away emissions, dust, noise and smoke [Holzer, S., 2011].

The stratum is placed at the border of the terrain, it being planted with different trees and bushes. The raised strata and their rich vegetation work as a visual barrier and protect the terrain from pollution. They turn into a *LIVING HEDGE* that assures a shelter and a living place for birds, hedgehogs, insects and others. The barriers of this type play a substantial role in encouraging

useful animal and insect communities, achieving *de facto* a **specific bio community**.

Exemplification of terraces with specific bio community, that may include: - culture of vegetables and fruit; - culture of mushrooms; - fish breeding; - animal breeding / grazing (ex.: balanced bio community of pigs, ducks, toads, that reduce snails and slugs that eat mushrooms) and other elements of policulture. In figures 8 and 9 there are caught edifying images (source: Sepp Holzer – *Permacultura - site*).

Fig. 8.
Pumpkin raised in the microclimate from a stone

Fig. 9.
Mushroom cultivation on tree trunks or logs

Conclusions

Generic awareness of the *modulization process* means an important step for the productive activity in the future, especially if we take into account the climate, ecologic, economic and social provocations, i.e. the complementary transition from Green Economy to Blue Economy, by obtaining mountain alimentary and non alimentary eco-bio-products, as an expression of bioeconomy specific to sustainable development of the 21st century.

The permaculture concept represents the system that imitates Nature, *structurally* based on ecosystems and *functionally* on natural cycles with Mountain Modules well-structured applications. *The mountain module* may be regarded as a territorial "bio reactor" (the raw material, processed products and waste analyses), so that the newly acquired modular systemic structure may be *eMergetically* quantified on the principles of integronic management.

The permacultural system is adapted to the altitude gradient, distinguishing the of principle model for the permacultural landscape of average altitude (500-1600 m) and that one of high altitude (over 1600 m). The techniques of the permaculture system from the Romanian Carpathians are based on terraces, raised strata,

hedges etc., that allow to implement policulture, that leads to achieving complex bio communities which permanently sustain a balanced biodiversity that *de facto* imitates nature.

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MINERAL COMPOSITION STUDY OF COMPLEX ADDITIVES OF BAKERY PRODUCTS WITH ANTI-DIABETIC APPOINTMENT

U. Chomanov, G. Zhumaliyeva, A. Shoman, G. Nurynbetova

Abstract: *In Kazakhstan, one of the most consumed products are baked goods, in connection with the increase in their range with anti-diabetic appointment is an important task, because increasing every year in Kazakhstan people with diabetes.*

One of the efficient ways to solve this problem is to develop a high technology manufacturing bakery products anti-diabetic action using a set of Herbal Supplements to solve this problem requires the use of biotechnology and electrical methods in the production of complex additives used in bakery products anti-diabetic action. The authors have developed the technology of bakery products anti-diabetic action using a set of Herbal Supplements (rose, Jerusalem artichoke, stevia leaf, celery root) using biotechnology and electrical methods. The mineral composition of the reference bread with addition of the complex supplements 5,10, 15 and 20% by weight of water. According to studies established that these minerals (sodium, silicon, phosphorus, sulfur, chlorine, potassium, iron) in wheat bread with the addition of the complex supplements with 15% replacement of water dominate over the other samples. It was found that due to the consumption of bread with the addition of complex supplements with 15% water changes a person covers the daily requirement of phosphorus, chlorine and iron more than the norm of the daily intake of minerals. It is noted that the sulfur - the necessary structural component of some amino acids are also included in the composition of insulin and is involved in its formation. Need approximately 1 g per day. The daily requirement for sulfur by 8%. Studies have shown that wheat bread with complex supplements with 15% replacement of water contains rich mineral composition. On the basis of laboratory tests obtained wheat bread with complex supplements with 15% replacement of the water produced by biotechnological methods and electro contains rich mineral composition and provides a bakery anti-diabetic action.

Keywords: *complex supplements, mineral composition, the daily need, bread, electrophysical methods, biotechnological methods, minerals, anti-diabetic action.*

1. Introduction

Prevention and treatment of diabetes mellitus (DM) are still valid. Currently, the prevalence of diabetes in the world is from 2 to 5%, and in the age groups over 60 years reaches 10.8% [1]. According to the Ministry of Health, the country suffers from diabetes, more than 157 000 people, of which II diabetes type - 92% and the first type - 8%: both lead to serious consequences. According to recent reports in the world about 145 million people suffer from diabetes, and, as predicted by scientists, their number may increase by 2025 to 300 million. DM - endocrine-metabolic diseases, which is based on insulin deficiency. Risk factors for the disease diabetes with hereditary predisposition to it, are long-term abuse of foods containing carbohydrate (sugar, jam, pastries), systematic overeating, obesity, over-nervous system trauma, infectious diseases, atherosclerosis, hypertension, acute and chronic

pancreatic disease. An integral part of diabetes treatment is diet therapy. Patients with diabetes need to build power with the physiological needs of the body, depending on body weight, age, physical activity, occupation and place of residence, and also depending on the severity of the disease and the presence of comorbidities and complications. Diet should contain an increased amount of B vitamins and ascorbic acid. The protein content shall be within the physiological norms, but his administration should be individualized. The diet should include the limitation of animal fats and carbohydrates by reducing consumption of sugar and sugar products. At present, the market for goods has improved markedly diabetic destination [1]. There are new sweeteners and confectionary products (cookies, cakes, candies) made on their basis. This is mainly foreign-made products, and

often they contain sugar substitutes do not have permission from the Ministry of Health for use in Kazakhstan. Also known adverse side effects of some of them - sodium cyclamate, acesulfame, and saccharin sodium. In Kazakhstan there are only a few companies that produce products for diabetics. However, their relatively limited range, and, moreover, these products are quite expensive and are not available for most patients. Especially small selection of baked goods (MKI) diabetic destination and their quality does not always meet the medical requirements. The food industry has a strong interest in the use of non-traditional vegetable raw materials in the production of bakery products. One such plant is Stevia, a sweet taste which is caused by substances glycoside forms, organized under the title "stevioside" (200-300 times sweeter than sugar). These components have been isolated and studied in 1955, but only became widely used now. Stevia is widely used in Japan, China, Thailand and USA. According to studies Stevia contains up to 10% sweet glycosides, 11-15% protein, vitamins, including vitamin C, and minerals. This product has no calorific value, will not increase the blood glucose level. Known for its use in the treatment of inflammatory diseases of the stomach, as an antitumor agent, as a means of strengthening blood vessels, normalizing the liver, gallbladder. Outwardly stevia syrup used in the treatment of dermatitis, seborrhea and other skin diseases [1]. Other vegetable raw materials containing a unique carbohydrate complex is Sweet. Especially valuable presence in Jerusalem artichoke essential amino acids, dietary fiber, pectin, nitrogenous substances, vitamins B and C. The use of artichoke in diabetes mild and moderate severity normalizes carbohydrate metabolism and lowers by 30-40% the level of cholesterol in the blood [1]. No less promising product is celery. Celery refers to a group of plants with high content of vitamin C. Also, celery found in folic acid in an amount of up to 3.0 mg / kg and about 8 free amino acids, among them, such as asparagine, tyrosine. The protein is 30-50% of crude protein. According to the literature [2] mentioned celery contains potassium, sodium, calcium, phosphorus, and a small amount of iron and copper. The presence of celery in a large number of alkaline salts improves digestion of protein foods, regulation of metabolism and the maintenance of acid-base balance in the body, protecting it from premature aging. Celery helps to whet the appetite, a

beneficial effect on the nervous system and sleep, it is used in medicine for the treatment of obesity.

A favorable combination of minerals and a high content of potassium promotes the excretion of uric acid. Celery cell enhances the gastrointestinal system, accelerates the excretion of cholesterol and thus protects a person from atherosclerosis. Celery contains volatile, which reduces the activity of spoilage microorganisms, protecting the human body from various diseases [2]. From these data it can be concluded about the rich nutrient content of celery. Other vegetable raw materials, have medicinal properties is a rose. On the merits of food and medicinal properties of rosehip knew back in the IV century BC in ancient Greece. In Russia XVI-XVII centuries offer expeditions to collect wild rose as a medicinal plant in the Orenburg steppe. Thus, the therapeutic properties of wild rose are time-tested and results. Useful properties of rosehip due to its chemical composition [3]. Rose hips are a real treasury of vital substances - vitamins, pectin, organic acids, minerals. The content of pectic substances depending on the species and varieties, the range from 1.5 to 6.2%. Phenolic compounds that determine the value of P-vitamin rose, represented by catechins, leucanthocyanins, phenolic acids, anthocyanins, flavonols. The predominance leucoanthocyanins (0.6-2.1%) and catechins (0,4-1,9%) results in a high biological value fruits [4]. Rosehip - a wonderful plant, all parts of which can help in various diseases. For example, the roots can help with heart disease, disorders of the stomach and so on. The stalk of rose hips can be used with radiculitis, etc. Flowers of artisanal plants can help in inflammatory processes, but the berries are used to enhance immunity, as well as diabetes. They are well lower blood pressure and cholesterol levels, as well as dramatically improve the health of people suffering from insulin deficiency. The presence of a large number of different dog rose vitamins, especially vitamin C, trace elements and helps to maintain the body in diabetes in tone. All his substance beneficial effect on the body by fatigue that is of great help for patients with diabetes of all kinds. Since diabetes suffer certain organs in the human body, such as the kidney, then to improve their performance and, if necessary, removal of kidney stones can be applied drug, the main component of which is the root of the hips [4].

Thus, due to the presence of organic acids, vitamins, amino acids in vegetable raw materials

(Jerusalem artichoke, celery root, rose hips, stevia leaf) the authors developed a set of Herbal Supplements (Jerusalem artichoke, celery root, rose hips, stevia leaf) with the use of the use of biotechnology and electrophysical methods,

which improves food and biological value of bakery products. The use of these raw materials in the creation of supplements in high technology in the production of bakery products antidiabetic action is actual direction.

2. Materials and methods

The object of the study are bakery antidiabetic action. Base 'test regional laboratory of engineering profile "Constructional and biochemical materials" RSE on PVC "South-Kazakhstan State University im.M. Auezova "is equipped with modern instruments to determine the mineral composition of bakery products with

the addition of an anti-diabetic action of the complex Supplements 5-20% by weight vody. Eksperimentalnye studies were performed using Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry with kadrupolnym mass analyzer Varian 820MS (USA).

Fig. 1. Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry with a quadrupole mass analyzer Varian 820MS (USA)

Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry Varian ICP-MS designed for the measurement of various elements in the samples of substances and materials, solutions, food, soil, etc. Scope - geology, metallurgy, chemical industry, nuclear power, environmental control, food industry and scientific research. Description: Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry Varian ICP-MS are stationary laboratory instruments, consisting of an ion source, mass analyzer, the registration system and automatic control system based on IBM - compatible computer. The ion source consists of a horizontal burner, inductively coupled plasma and a system for sampling ions from the plasma

and feeding them into the mass analyzer. The ion source is equipped with a special system that creates a parabolic electrostatic field in the plasma region - "ion mirror" that guides the ions to the mass analyzer entrance. In this case, uncharged particles and photons pass freely through the ion mirror. The separation of ions according to mass to charge ratio is carried out using a quadrupole mass analyzer, which enables rapid scanning of the spectrum. Signal detection is performed using a multiplier which provides a dynamic range up to 10⁹. Managing the process of measurement and processing output data in devices carried by an IBM-compatible computer with a special software package.

3. Results and discussion Studies

Grain products are a staple of the human diet. In bread contains many nutrients necessary for man; Among them, proteins carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals, dietary fiber. Due breads man almost completely covers the need for iron derive a significant portion of

manganese and phosphorus. A major shortcoming of mineral complex bread is low content of calcium and its unfavorable ratio of phosphorus and magnesium. In the bread contained an insufficient quantity of potassium, chromium, cobalt and other elements. Therefore, increasing the value of the mineral is also an

urgent problem [5]. Lack of plants and minerals in food determines flow minerals in the body. Therefore, the shortfall ca minerals with dietary supplements. The aim of our study was to evaluate the mineral composition in the production of bakery products for diabetic patients with the use of additives from vegetable raw materials (stevia, Jerusalem artichoke, celery root, rose hips). As a base used wheat bread. The additives were added Supplements complex prepared by the use of biochemical and electrophysical method. Baked wheat bread dough method using complex Supplements humidity 42.0% of flour, water, yeast and salt. In experimental embodiments in an amount of 5,10, 15 and 20% by weight of water.

Sample 1 - the bread with addition of the complex supplements 5% by weight of water.

Sample 2 - the bread with addition of the complex supplements 10% by weight of water.

Sample 3 - bread with addition of the complex supplements 15% by weight of water.

Sample 4 - bread with addition of the complex supplements 20% by weight of water.

Control - bread from flour of first grade.

The results showed that the complex supplements may be used in the process dough

method: An Introduction to the amount of 5-20% by weight of water increases the accumulation of acidity, which creates prerequisites for reducing the duration of fermentation test, fermentation test is more evenly, resulting in an increase in the index the porosity of the finished bread. The obtained data suggest the possible use of vegetable raw materials for the production of diabetic destination. The authors found that phisico-chemical and organoleptic properties was selected wheat bread with complex supplements with 15% water change. We have studied the mineral composition of the reference bread with addition of the complex supplements 5,10, 15 and 20% by weight of water. The variety of functions of minerals in the human body (regulation of water metabolism, maintenance of acid-base balance, secretion of digestive glands, participation in the process of hematopoiesis, etc.) determines the need for inclusion in the general assessment of the nutritional value of bread its mineral value [6]. Table 1 shows the mineral composition of wheat bread with the addition of complex supplements. Table 2 presents the daily demand for minerals according to the literature [7].

Table 1. *Mineral composition of bread with the addition of complex Supplement*

Indicators name	Control	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4
samples weight, g	18,1698	20,2080	24,0356	15,9608	14,9670
Ash of samples, r	0,2223	0,2570	0,3214	0,200	0,1880
Ash, %	1,223	1,27	1,337	1,253	1,256
Na, g / kg	2,93	2,96	3,07	2,94	2,93
Mg, g / kg	0,26	0,31	0,35	0,27	0,32
Si, g / kg	0,02	0,02	0,02	0,025	0,02
P, g / kg	1,06	1,22	1,34	1,07	1,27
S, g / kg	0,061	0,07	0,05	0,08	0,07
Cl, g / kg	2,79	2,68	2,77	2,84	2,47
K, g / kg	0,84	0,93	0,92	0,93	0,88
Ca, g / kg	0,18	0,19	0,21	0,19	0,21
Fe, g / kg	0,01	0,01	0,007	0,06	0,01

Table 2. *Daily demand for minerals*

Minerals	Daily nutrition
Na, g	3
Mg, g	400
Si, mg	30
P, mg	800
S, g	He y c T aH o
Cl, mg	750
K, g	3
Ca, g	400
Fe, mg	15

Conclusions

According to the results of Table 1 shows that these minerals (sodium, silicon, phosphorus, sulfur, chlorine, potassium, iron) in wheat bread with the addition of the complex supplements with 15% replacement of water dominate over the other samples.

Due to the consumption of bread man covers the daily requirement of sodium, magnesium, silicon, potassium, calcium, respectively, 97.7; 0.07; 83.3; 31; 0.05%. A phosphorus, chlorine and iron cover the daily needs of man more than the norm, respectively, at 33.75; 378; 400%.

It is noted that the sulfur - the necessary structural component of some amino acids are also included in the composition of insulin and is involved in its formation.

Need approximately 1 g per day [8]. The daily requirement for sulfur by 8%. Studies have shown that wheat bread with complex supplements with 15% replacement of water contains rich mineral composition.

On the basis of laboratory tests wheat bread with complex supplements with 15% replacement

of water produced by biotechnological and electrical methods, contains rich mineral composition, and provides a bakery antidiabetic action.

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DEVELOPMENT OF THE FOOD SECTOR IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

A. STRATAN¹, V. MOROZ, A. IGNAT, E. LUCASENCO

Abstract: *The food sector of the Republic of Moldova has undergone significant changes in the past decades. Food processing companies and large scale collective and state farms have been privatized, markets were liberalized, and economies have been integrated into the global food systems. As a result of liberalization and privatization processes, the state-controlled vertical integration in the agri-food industry had collapse.*

Latter on, private vertical coordination systems have emerged and started to grow rapidly as a response to consumer demand for food quality and safety on the one hand and the farms' production constraints caused by factor market imperfection on the other. The main drivers of the integration processes are private business operators and traders. However, the efficiency of the newly emerged food value chains is still low. This investigation was based on analysis of the official statistical data, qualitative and quantitative studies and other relevant publications. A significant part of analysis was done in the framework of the FP7 project "AGRICISTRADO". In this paper the importance and the most recent changes of the food industry in the Republic of Moldova were demonstrated, the main impediments were analyzed and proposals to foster the food sector development were provided.

Keywords: *food sector, agriculture, food consumption, agri food trade.*

1. Introduction

Global transformation and modernization of the food sector in the Republic of Moldova has faced several challenges over the past decades when the country started a complex processes of transformation of political and economic systems, such as liberalization of exchange rates, prices, and privatization of enterprises and agricultural holdings, which caused a collapse of the system of vertical coordination and significant disruptions in the agri-food chain.

Disruptions in relationships between farmers, input suppliers and food businesses also resulted in serious constraints faced by many farms and processors in accessing basic inputs. At the same time the food export is represented mainly by primary agricultural commodities or semi-processed food products.

The purpose of this article is to assess the impact of recent changes and identify possible solutions for strengthening the resilience of the food sector against external trade shocks.

2. Material and methods

Given the challenges of the recent development in food sector the following

research methods were used: analysis of the food sector structure and development tendencies, analysis of the legal framework regulation the food safety system in the Republic of Moldova, analysis of the food distribution system and country's food security, analysis of the export development trends for main groups of agri-food products, analysis of the impact of external shocks over the export development and country's economic stability and food security.

The main sources of primary information for this study were data from the publications of the National Bureau of Statistics of the Republic of Moldova and the data bases of the National Bureau of Statistics of the Republic of Moldova. As a secondary source of information a range of articles and studies elaborated by local and foreign experts were used.

3. Results and discussion

The prospects for continued growth in demand for value-added food and agricultural products constitute an incentive for increased attention to agro industries development within the context of economic growth, food security and poverty-fighting strategies (da Silva, 2009).

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Despite the de-industrialization process that lasted almost two decades in Moldova, the industry has maintained its position as an important sector of the national economy and as a foundation for the continuous development of the country. The leading positions in the structure of industrial production belong to the branches specialized in the processing of local raw material, mainly of agricultural origin. The food processing sector involves about 1,260 companies. The share of food industry accounted for about 43% of the total industrial production in the Republic of Moldova in 2013, although this share was 52% in 2004 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2014).

In the same time the large scale food industry is characterized by underutilization of its capacities and insufficient investments. High levels of moral and physical depreciation of the industrial capacities and infrastructure is typical for local food processing companies. A large part of processing equipment and technologies is not energy efficient and do not meet modern standards. Many enterprises lack modern

management practices and necessary investment capital. The lack of financial resources leads to inadequate compensation and to the exodus of the skilled labour force. Lack of horizontal and vertical coordination of supply chains is another important reason underlying the low competitiveness of the agri-food sector.

The reasons causing low prices of agricultural products include poor development of wholesale markets, low bargaining power, changing product quality, lack of distribution channels, poor infrastructure and limited access to foreign markets. Value chain deficiencies lead to large discrepancies between the farm gate price and the consumer price, resulting in low-income, low investment and persistently low quality at the farm level.

Despite favourable circumstances in international markets the development of food sector of the Republic of Moldova had an unstable character. Production volume of food and beverage industry in 2013 amounted to only about 87% of production in 2005 (see Table 1).

Table 1. Indices of industrial production, by most important types of activities, 2006-2013 (2005 = 100%)(Source: BNS, 2014)

	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
Industry – total, of which:	95,2	94,0	95,4	75,2	82,2	90,1	88,3	94,3
Processing industry, of which	93,5	91,8	92,8	71,7	79,5	88,8	87,4	94,3
Manufacture of food products and beverages	81,6	75,2	82,0	67,6	75,7	80,9	82,0	87,2
Production, processing and preserving of meat and meat products	109,8	142,8	147,1	121,8	132,5	150,7	174,2	179,4
Processing and preserving of fruits and vegetables	106,5	115,6	109,2	84,1	90,4	118,0	98,0	111,4
Manufacture of dairy products	98,2	101,7	108,3	98,2	107,1	109,3	117,3	127,7
Manufacture of products of flour-milling industry, of starches and starch products	106,5	95,1	105,0	88,7	81,6	80,3	70,5	85,9
Manufacture of bred and pastry products	106,4	118,0	129,1	121,2	127,6	137,3	136,5	143,2
Manufacture of wine	50,9	36,3	45,2	35,7	40,3	41,2	41,9	38,8

However this decrease was mostly due to the reduction of wine production after the restrictions imposed by Russian Federation for Moldovan wine exports in 2006.

The most important products of the food processing sector include wine, meat, fruit and

vegetable products, dairy products and bakery products.

Wine and brandy production. Wine and distilled spirits represent the largest portion of Moldova's food processing and a significant part of all industrial output. Moldova had 98 enterprises dealing with wine production and

bottling in 2013. In addition, there were 18 factories producing, maturing and bottling distillates. Grapes are grown by about 70,000 individuals, mostly smallholder farmers.

Mills and bakeries. There were 241 mills and 278 bakeries operating in the country in 2013. A concentration of producers grouping around the large bread-baking plants that have a market share of about 65% can be observed in the sector; the group of small and medium scale bakeries has a market share of circa 35%. As main leaders in this sector can be mentioned “Franzeluta” SA located in the capital city, the bread baking factory from Balti in the North region and the bread baking factory “Cahul Pan” SA in the South.

Fruit and vegetable processing. Fruit and vegetable processors can be divided into two main groups: the first comprises a small number of large firms, focused on export markets and producing about 80% of the total output of the sector; and about 80 small and medium canneries mainly serving the domestic market. Together these firms process from 150,000 to 200,000 tons of raw material, mainly apples, plums and vegetables. The main products are concentrated apple juice, fruit and tomato paste, canned fruits and vegetables. However, the potential of the fruit and vegetable processing industry is utilized at only one third of its capacity.

Meat processing. Moldova’s meat-processing industry is highly consolidated, while official statistical data indicate there were 159 meat processing enterprises and production units in 2013. “Carmez” in Chisinau and “Basarabia Nord” in Balti dominate the domestic market,

together controlling about 2/3 of the local market. Along with “Carmez International” (Belgian joint venture now separated from “Carmez”), these companies dominate the export market and have strong brands. All these three companies import about 85-95% of their meat and offal raw material and nearly all of their ingredients used for manufacture of sausages and ham. A handful of other manufacturers supply sausages and smoked meats to the supermarket and small shop outlets in cities and towns.

Meat companies operate their abattoirs on an intermittent basis, because domestic stock is more expensive than imported frozen meat. The production of the processing industry is exported mainly to the CIS states. Moldova has not qualified for the status needed to export meat products to the EU.

Dairy production. The dairy industry is based primarily on the supply of raw milk from small producers, company-owned collection centres and dairy cooperatives with collection centres financed by the dairy companies or through donor programs. While overall milk supply is adequate and animal productivity has been increasing slowly, dairy processors have seen only marginal improvements in the quality of milk. A number of 32 dairy companies operated in the Republic of Moldova in 2013.

Prices and production costs for the most important processed food products are not presented by the official statistics of the Republic of Moldova. The available aggregated data from the national accounts confirm that agri-food sector produces mostly raw materials and semi-processed products.

Table 2. Value added in agriculture and selected food industries, 2007-2013, millions MDL

		2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
A,B	Agriculture, hunting, forestry and pisciculture	5333,9	5544,0	5134,5	8657,4	10095,2	9896,2	12383,1
D15	Manufacture of food products and beverages	2381,5	2768,8	2516,0	3086,0	3682,9	3974,3	4315,3
D15.1	Production, processing and preserving of meat and meat products	24,0	293,2	273,8	300,5	393,1	472,0	50,5
D15.3	Processing and preserving of fruits and vegetables	259,5	226,4	201,9	245,1	427,4	370,3	420,2
D15.5	Manufacture of dairy products	227,5	269,0	30,3	344,4	380,9	429,9	481,8

The ratio between the value added in agriculture and agri-food industry shows that during the recent years the value added in

agriculture is higher than value added created in the food processing industry - more than 2.4 times on average for the period of 2007-2013

(see Figure 1). At the same time, food processing industry has higher productivity as compared with the agricultural production.

Legal framework

The food safety system in the Republic of Moldova is currently being revised to comply with the EU regulations on food safety.

The Food Law was adopted in 2004 and reflects most of the provisions of Regulation (EC) No. 178/2002. This law creates the legal framework for the implementation of the EU legislation on foodstuffs.

Fig. 1. The ratio between value added in agriculture and agri-food industry, 2007-2013

Sources: elaborated by authors based on data from National Accounts of the National Bureau of Statistics, 2014

The scope of the food law is to protect human health and consumers' rights and facilitate trade. The law establishes general requirements for the safe production, distribution, import and export of foodstuffs, for traceability of foods, for risk assessment and for establishing a rapid alert system. It also defines the responsibilities of food business operators to produce and distribute food in good hygienic conditions, to introduce the HACCP control system, to label foodstuffs and to provide sufficient information to consumers.

Food safety is also the subject of the Law on Sanitary-Epidemiological Assurance of the Population (1993, rev. 2003), which includes mandatory hygiene training for food handlers, sanitary authorization for food establishments and sanitary certification of food.

The Law on Sanitary Veterinary Activity (2007) establishes requirements for animal health, prevention of diseases, sanitary/veterinary control and inspections in the area of food of animal origin, monitoring of veterinary residues and organization of activities in the field of veterinary medicine.

The Law on Identification and Registration of Animals (2006) is on the way of implementation. The Law on Plant Protection (1999) establishes requirements for plant health and protection from diseases and pests. The Law on Protection of Consumers (2003) establishes requirements for

the protection of consumers, for accurate information and for consumers' rights.

One of the most recent laws is the Law 113 from 18.05.2012 on the establishment of principles and general requirements of the legislation regarding the food safety. The general objectives of the food safety legislation are to achieve a high level of protection of human life and health, consumer interests, fair practices in food trade, taking into account animal health and welfare, plant health and environmental protection; to facilitate trade between Moldova and other countries; manufacture and marketing of food and feed in accordance with the objectives and general principles of the law.

National Strategy for Food Safety for the years 2011-2015 creates preconditions for the adoption of the principles of the EU food safety and implementation of an integrated approach "farm to fork" in order to ensure public health and increase exports. A remarkable result of this strategy was the creation of the Food Safety

National Agency in 2012, which took over full control of food safety in Moldova, thus overcoming existing constraints related to the overlapping of functions and repetitive procedures in the field. However, one of the weaknesses of this strategic document, which may create problems in achieving longer-term goals, is the insufficient level of objective measuring and achievement.

Food distribution

Distribution of food products in Moldova still relies on traditional markets, with recent occurrence of supermarkets in large cities. There are currently about 190 supermarkets and three “Metro Cash and Carry” stores dealing with trade of food products. According to the estimates made by local experts, about 10-20% of Moldova's population buys food in supermarkets. Respectively, the larger urban centres are, the greater is the share of supermarkets in food products sales. The most developed retail chains in the Republic of Moldova are “Fourchette”, “Green Hills”, “N1”, “Fidesco”, “Metro Cash & Carry”, “IMC Market”, “Linella”, “Cvin” and “Everest”. According to the interviewed experts, about 20-40% of food purchases are made in about 1,000 small grocery stores that are located near the place of residence. Many of these stores do not sell a full range of fruits and vegetables that occupy less than 3% of the commercial space. Moldavians usually procure foodstuffs at open-air agricultural markets, seasonal fairs and from the street vendors. However, in rural areas considerable part of the food products is produced for own consumption. Currently, the distribution network of fresh products comprises 3 wholesale agricultural markets in Chisinau and one in Balti, 12 retail agricultural markets in Chisinau, plus other 38 regional agricultural markets and more than 100 local agri-food markets. Overall, wholesale food markets that currently exist in Moldova are poorly equipped and under obsolete standards because they provide just a simple place for sale and have limited storage capacities. In some cases, the sales areas are not covered, only offering parking for transport from where sales are operated. As a consequence, the role of these wholesale markets is quite limited.

Food consumption

At the national level Republic of Moldova is food secure. It produces the main food products, exports surplus food, and imports necessary food to meet its food requirements. Food security indicators prove that in the Republic of Moldova the level of per capita food consumption has stabilized during the last years. At the same time, the level of consumption is much lower than in neighbouring countries or in other East European countries.

The food security challenges in the Republic of Moldova have two major dimensions. The first dimension seeks to maintain and increase the country's ability to meet the national food demands through assurance of the internal food production, import of the food products that can not be produced efficiently in the country, and exports of products that have a comparative advantage. The second dimension is related to the reduction of the increasing inequalities and expansion of the poverty among the majority of the households of the Republic of Moldova that is manifested by inadequate and unstable food supplies, low purchasing power, weak institutional support networks, weak food emergency management systems and unemployment.

In addition to natural risks, commercial risks largely influence the level of food security in the Republic of Moldova. The evolution of prices in Moldova follows the trends of international food prices of agricultural products and resources necessary for agricultural production. Like other small countries with low income, Republic of Moldova faces additional challenges to restructure and modernize the sector of primary production and processing industry in order to supply the local market with basic food products.

The level of food self-sufficiency of the country is rather high, however in several years it decreased to a critical level due to severe droughts (see Table 3).

Table 3. *Self-sufficiency rate (%), 2006-2013*

	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
Cereals	99,2	70,6	143,4	105,0	117,8	115,6	60,8	150,3
Sunflower	145,0	65,5	178,0	121,4	156,6	195,9	143,8	326,3
Potatoes	91,7	67,0	93,4	89,4	100,4	116,2	66,6	89,8
Vegetables	103,5	84,8	110,1	98,6	104,2	100,5	93,3	102,4
Fruits	195,8	227,0	222,2	213,9	207,7	237,7	245,2	264,2
Grapes	102,4	106,8	102,6	104,3	104,6	102,8	103,9	103,7
Meat	67,8	84,5	67,8	86,7	86,0	86,1	81,5	69,8
Eggs	112,7	101,6	100,0	100,3	98,8	95,4	102,2	98,0
Milk and milk products	97,5	95,0	97,1	95,0	94,1	92,0	84,7	86,8

Food export

Food sector represents one of the pillars of the national economic development of the Republic of Moldova. The export structure is dominated by a few groups of products which reflect a rather

primitive structure of the agri-food exports in which prevails wine production and raw material of plant origin such as nuts, grains and oil seeds (see Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Most important groups of exported food products of the Republic of Moldova 2004-2012, Mil. USD. Sources: National Bureau of Statistics, 2014

The main export destination countries for these groups of products are Russia, Ukraine, Belarus, Romania, Italy, France and Spain. Out of these four major groups of products only two, namely "Oil seeds" and "Vegetable oil" were not

included in the restriction list imposed by Russian authorities. While external trade with other two groups of products was seriously affected by these restrictions. Title of paper

Fig. 3. Structure of agri-food exports of the Republic of Moldova by major products and trading partners in 2012

Agri-food exports of Republic of Moldova have been strongly marked by a significant reduction of supplies to Russia in 2001-2008 and the embargo in 2013. In 2013, more than one quarter of Moldovan export revenues originated from Russia. Currently, Russia uses this economic leverage to exercise pressure on Moldova through a number of trade restrictions.

Conclusions

- The agro-food sector in the Republic of Moldova is characterized by weak links between primary agricultural production, processing industry and trade sector, underutilization of the production capacities,

lack of investments, outdated equipment and standards.

- There are positive trends in the development of the agri-food sector of the Republic of Moldova during the last years. However the vulnerability of this sector to natural, economic and commercial risks remains to be very high.
- The level of country's food security for major agri-food products has stabilized during the last years. Nevertheless in several years it decreases to a critical level due to negative impact of natural hazards. Trade restrictions exacerbated by natural calamities could increase the risk of food insecurity.
- The current situation in the international trade with agri-food products placed the Republic of Moldova in a difficult position. Exchange of sanctions between a number of Western countries and the Russian Federation provides multiple restrictions on the conduct of economic activities, including international trade that makes it necessary to review existing economic policies. Prohibitions and restrictions on the part of the Russian Federation on the import of agricultural products from the Republic of Moldova are forcing the government to urgently diversify export markets and to take measures to strengthen the economic security of the country.
- The food sector of the Republic of Moldova needs specific actions in order to stimulate

development of the high value agriculture through creation of product sales centres, strengthening quality control, organizing regional wholesale markets, assisting producers to sell their products, development of market infrastructure at central level, development of the post harvest and market infrastructure.

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EGG SURFACE DECONTAMINATION BY USING HIGH VOLTAGE PULSED, COLD ATMOSPHERIC PLASMA JETS

L. APOSTOL¹, N. GEORGESCU², I. VĂTUIU¹, L. GACEU³

Abstract: Cold atmospheric gas plasma treatment (CAP) is an alternative approach for the decontamination of termosensible and minimally processed food. In this study, *Salmonella Enteritidis* serovar Typhimurium (*S. Typhimurium*) have been treated with high voltage pulsed, cold atmospheric plasma jets. The plasma jets were ejected from discharge plasmas in He-O₂ gas mixture, at atmospheric pressure.

The contaminated eggshell surface was of about 1 cm². Furthermore, the efficacy of CAP treatment for decontaminating egg surfaces inoculated with *S. Typhimurium* was evaluated. After a 5 min. plasma treatment, the microorganisms have been totally destroyed. No negative effects of the plasma treatment on egg quality were observed.

Keywords: Cold atmospheric gas plasma, *Salmonella typhimurium*, egg, microbial inactivation, surface decontamination.

1. Introduction

Extensive research on the use of cold atmospheric plasmas to inactivate microorganisms on food surfaces is a relatively recent event.

These plasmas make the decontamination process practical, inexpensive and suitable for applications when product preservation is desired. This work is referring to the egg surface decontamination.

The cold atmospheric plasma has major advantages in comparison to the alternative methods of egg decontamination. First of all, the simple washing of category A eggs is forbidden through Commission Regulation (European Community) No 2295/2003.

2. Materials and Methods

The main classical decontamination methods include chemical, thermal and radiation ones. However, such treatments are not sustainable given that chemical products can be absorbed by egg shells, and contaminate egg content.

Thermal processes affect egg content or lead to shell cracking.

Slow pasteurisation is far too time-consuming for widespread use in the modern egg producing installation.

Also, irradiation of eggs is a disputed decontamination method in the European Union.

Fig. 1. The source of high voltage pulsed, cold atmospheric plasma jets

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The plasma source has a coaxial structure (Fig. 1). The plasma is produced in a discharge chamber, by applying high voltage pulses between two electrodes:

1) The high voltage electrode is an axial syringe needle, of 150 mm length, and 1.2/1.6 mm input/output diameter;

2) The ground electrode is a 40 mm length copper cylinder, mounted at 10 mm distance from the plasma exit hole, on a Teflon structure which has 6/8 mm input/output diameter.

The syringe needle tip is axially placed, at 12 mm distance from the plasma exit hole.

The discharge chamber is inside the Teflon structure, along the ground electrode. The high voltage pulses (20 – 25 kV amplitude, 200 ns width, 100 pulses per second) generate a

dielectric barrier discharge, in a He-O₂ gas mixture.

The helium gas, which facilitates the occurrence of electric discharges at atmospheric pressure, is introduced in the discharge chamber through a lateral orifice.

The helium flow rate is of 2.5 l/min. The oxygen gas is introduced through the syringe needle, with flow rates of 12.5 – 50 ml/min, so that its concentration in the helium gas is of 0.5 – 2 %.

The oxygen role is to chemically activate the discharge plasma, in order to have a strong bactericidal effect.

The helium flow pushes the discharge plasma out, forming the plasma jet (Fig. 2d). The plasma exit hole has 2 mm diameter.

Fig. 2: **a)** Untreated egg. **b), c)** The outer (**b)** and the inner (**c)** eggshell surface samples formed microorganism colonies. Conclusion: the untreated eggs are contaminated. **d)** Plasma treatment. **e), f)** The outer (**e)** and the inner (**f)** eggshell surface samples did not form microorganism colonies. Conclusion: the plasma treated eggs are decontaminated.

Results

The main chemically active agents are oxygen atoms and the OH radicals. It is well known that these agents easily interact with microorganisms cells giving rise to oxidizing reactions.

Oxygen atoms are generated by electron-O₂ interaction. OH radicals are the result of the electrons and oxygen-atoms reactions with the water molecules from the air which the plasma jet encounters.

By spectral analysis, an optimization of the O₂ concentration in the helium gas has been

achieved. The chemical activity of the plasma jet has been estimated by the intensity of the O I 777 nm emission spectrum line.

This intensity is maximized for 1 % molecular oxygen concentration in the helium gas.

In order to verify the effectiveness of the plasma treatment for the eggs superficial decontamination, a target pathogen has been deliberately inoculated onto the surface of the eggs.

The choice of the pathogen was based on the fact that *Salmonella* has long been recognized as

an important zoonotic pathogen of economic significance in animals and humans.

An egg surface of about 1 cm² (Fig. 2a) has been contaminated with a solution containing *Salmonella enterica* ATCC 14028 (7.7×10^3 CFU/ml – CFU denotes Colony-Forming Units). The treatment has been made with high voltage pulsed, cold atmospheric plasma jets (Fig. 2d). The high voltage pulses had 20 kV amplitude. The helium and oxygen flow rates were of 2.5 l/min, and 25 ml/min, respectively. The treatment time was of 5 min.

After the plasma treatment, both the untreated and the treated eggs have been maintained for 24 h at 37° C. Afterwards, microorganism detaching techniques were used for the external/internal eggshell surface.

The obtained samples were spread onto agar in Petri dishes and incubated at 37° C for 24 h. After the incubation, the resulting microorganism colonies have been photographed.

For the untreated eggs, the samples from the external/internal eggshell surface formed microorganism colonies in the Petri dishes (Fig. 2 b, c).

This means that both the external and the internal eggshell surface were contaminated. For the treated eggs, the Petri dishes remained clean (Fig. 2 e, f), i.e. the high voltage pulsed, cold atmospheric plasma treatment totally destroyed *Salmonella enterica* from the eggshell surface.

No negative effects of this treatment on egg quality were observed.

Conclusions

Findings from this study indicate that cold atmospheric plasma is a new promising technique to decontaminate the eggs surface.

Our future research will be focused on the treatment of the whole egg surface, by immersing eggs in large volumes (liters) of cold atmospheric plasma.

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UNDERSTANDING THE RESTAURANTS CUSTOMERS. FOOD CHOICES AND BUSINESS IMPLICATIONS

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Abstract: *The paper aims at developing the knowledge base related to hospitality business customers by analyzing the customer satisfaction in relation to perceived food quality and characteristics. The customer satisfaction is a strong predictor of customer retention, image and word-of-mouth. Understanding the impact of food quality and characteristics on restaurant perception is a key step to customer satisfaction. A quantitative method is used to assess the customer perception and a fuzzy logic model gives a better representation of the results. It is also argued that cuisine and restaurant size have a statistically significant impact on restaurant perception. The article presents only part of the results of a larger study on customer behavior and satisfaction in relation to Braşov restaurants.*

Keywords: *customer satisfaction, restaurant perceptions, food quality, fuzzy model.*

1. Introduction

The restaurant market has become one of the most dynamic services markets worldwide. The needs expansion, the technological changes and globalization are forcing the restaurants to face great challenges and opportunities. It is an obvious increase in competition and the restaurants customers are having more opportunities than ever.

In this context the restaurants are trying to find ways to overcome the competitors and to create a stable flow of customers – new and repeat. A good starting point in this matter is a good understanding of the customers' needs and characteristics.

It has been argued that when discussing the need for customer satisfaction in the restaurant sector the customer perceptions about service quality is more important than prices perceptions (Iglesias, & Guillen, 2004), with the perceived price as a moderator between food quality and customer satisfaction (Ryu, & Han, 2010). The food perceived quality is a strong predictor for satisfaction and behavioral intentions (Namking, & Jan, 2007). In this situation, an emphasis on demographic, socio-economic characteristics, context and environment in relation to consumer decision process is welcomed (Sijtsema,

Linnemann, van Gaasbeek, Dagevos & Jongen, 2002; Anacleto, Barrento, Nunes, Rosa, & Marques, 2014). This is also important for restaurant owners as the return intent of restaurant customers is influenced by customer satisfaction related to food quality and atmosphere (Weiss, Feinstein, & Dalbor, 2004).

It is also important to realize that satisfied and repeated customers become free of charge positive advertisers for the restaurant. The word-of-mouth can become relevant on the web, given the trend of social media integration. Traditional and electronic word-of-mouth can be better achieved by offering satisfactory experiences with service employees (Jeong, & Jang, 2011). For the present article it is important to note that, in the light of the paper (Jeong, & Jang, 2011), the price perception does not have an important role in the customer satisfaction.

In order to achieve customer satisfaction a restaurant should focus on food presentation, tasty food, spatial seating arrangement, fascinating interior design, pleasing background music, reliable service, responsive service and competent employees (Namkung, & Jang, 2008). It has been shown that complementary service standards help boost the customer satisfaction

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(Khan, & Shaikh, 2011). Other perspectives are presenting the importance of core product, restaurant interior, personal, social meeting, company and restaurant atmosphere for a great restaurant experience (Hansen, Jensen, & Gustafsson, 2005).

From the customer point of view, starting with the decision making process (Pedraja, & Yague, 2001), the consumers are first choosing the food type and the food quality of the restaurant (Alonso, O'neill, Liu, & O'shea, 2013). As soon as those attributes were defined the customers looks for the restaurant style and atmosphere that best suits their expectations (Auty, 1992). The customer uses values like excellence, harmony, emotional stimulation and acknowledgement to assess the restaurant services (Jensen, & Hansen, 2007). There is an obvious connection between restaurant customers and tourists. Articles like "The customer perception of tourism services qualities" are presenting the importance of service quality in the hospitality industry and the cost of "silent killers" – the dissatisfied customers (Dănăilă, Dănăilă, & Gaceu, 2011).

Recent studies have shown that a fuzzy logic approach can help to better understand situations related to food and hospitality industry. Since its first presentation (Zadeh, 1965) and after several improvements in its methodology (Mamdani, 1976; Mamdani, 1977) the fuzzy sets, fuzzy logic and their applications proved to be able to extract relevant information for food industry

research fields like quality prediction (Birle, Hissein, & Becker, 2013), control and soft sensing applications (Han, Kim, Shim, & Lee, 2012) or service quality (Benitez, Martin, & Roman, 2007).

2. Research methodology

In order to obtain relevant information regarding the customer satisfaction and its determinates a quantitative research was developed. The target population was customers of restaurants situated in Brasov historical center. A number of 36 locations with 5610 (restaurants) NACE code were identified. A stratified sampling was used. Based on three restaurant characteristics (size, cuisine and street opening), a sample of 391 customers from 17 restaurants was questioned about their restaurant experience.

The sample is presented in table 1. Four restaurants categories were missing therefore four cells have 0 values. Using this sample method the relevance of the answers relative to the three considered characteristics is assured. The confidence level for this sample is 95% and the error is less than 5%.

The data were gathered between 26 and 28 December 2014, a period with an intense tourist activity in Brasov historical center. All the answers related to satisfaction questions used a scale from 1 to 10.

Table 1

	Cuisine					
	Romanian		International		Specialized	
	With street opening	Without street opening	With street opening	Without street opening	With street opening	Without street opening
Size						
<50 places	20	0	23	23	20	20
50 – 100 places	21	24	27	26	24	24
>100 places	46	0	71	0	22	0

3. Results

The average satisfaction score (restaurant perception) was 8.05. Several statistically significant differences between satisfaction score were identified. First, as presented in table 2, the

cuisine of the restaurant is relevant for the satisfaction score.

The data reveal a difference between the grades received by international restaurants (7.74), on one hand, and romanian (8.36) and specialized restaurants (8.20), on the other.

Table 2

Restaurant perception					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	30,318	2	15,159	5,620	,004
Within Groups	1046,659	388	2,698		
Total	1076,977	390			

Other statistically significant differences include:

- between large restaurants (7.50) and small (8.15) and medium (8.50);
- between genres and restaurant satisfaction – women's grades were better than man's (8.23 vs 7.87);
- between population income and restaurant satisfaction – higher income respondents reported better satisfaction with the restaurants (see table 3).

Table 3

		Restaurant perception
		Mean
Income	less than 250 euros	4,91
	250-500 euros	6,28
	500-1000 euros	8,21
	more than 1000 euros	9,55

Furthermore, when discussing restaurant perceptions, there were no statistically significant differences for several variables:

- between tourists and locals;
- between the score of the restaurants with no street opening and the ones with street opening;
- between tourists with different lengths of the visit;
- between the different marital statuses and ages of the respondents.

Using the grades received for food taste, food smell and food presentation a Pearson correlation was performed in order to assess the relation between customer satisfaction and these three food characteristics. All three coefficients are statistically significant and show a positive correlation between the variables. The strongest correlation is between restaurant perception and food presentation, followed by food taste and food smell. The complete data is presented in Table 4.

Table 4

Pearson Correlation	Food taste	Food smell	Food presentation
Restaurant perception	,839	,318	,958

Following the correlation results, a linear regression between restaurant perception (as explained variable) and food taste, food smell and food presentation (as independent variables) gives us an overview on how customer satisfaction is created. Table 5 shows the obtained results.

The only statistically irrelevant variable proves to be the food smell. Food taste and food presentation are significant with food presentation as a more powerful explanatory variable as food taste.

Table 5

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	,754	,108		6,957	,000
	Food_taste	,220	,018	,237	11,953	,000
	Food_smell	,014	,009	,020	1,500	,134
	Food_presentation	,734	,019	,767	37,880	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Restaurant perception

Given the previous results, for a better understanding of the impact the restaurant variables have on restaurant perception a fuzzy logic model was created. Fuzzy logic has several important advantages when it comes to dealing with non-crisp values.

The selected input variables were food taste and food presentation and the restaurant satisfaction was chosen as output variables. The model parameters were: “and” method – “min”, “or”

method – “max”, implication – “min”, aggregation – “max”, defuzzification – “centroid”. The fuzzification of the variables respected the 1 to 10 range used in the questionnaire but the membership functions were adjusted in order to provide an appropriate scale. All the variables were transformed into Gaussian fuzzy numbers based on a membership function as presented in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Membership function for “Taste” variable

The model was generated by using a set of 17 fuzzy rules that describe the restaurants customer behavior in relation with the two input variables. The rules were designed by analyzing the

coefficients of the previous regression in order to choose the right weight for each rule. The rules, the fuzzy process, the resulting function and it’s defuzzification is presented in figure 2.

Fig.2. Rule overview

For a better discussion of the model results the figure 3 is presenting the interaction between taste and presentation as independent variables and restaurant perception as dependent variable.

Fig. 3. Fuzzy correlation between food taste, food presentation and restaurant perception

Based on the above results several conclusions and recommendations can be obtained.

First, it is obvious that restaurant satisfaction can be obtained only by providing an outstanding service for several components. The choice to focus on a single restaurant or food characteristic is not going to provide an overall satisfaction. As

presented in figure 1, having a perfect score on one of the characteristics will generate a low satisfaction as long as the other has a poor score.

Second, we can argue that the best way to achieve customer satisfaction for a restaurant is to synchronize the development of the restaurant services and characteristics so that each

component has a similar increase. In figure 3 it is obvious that the top satisfaction can be achieved by using this strategy. At this point becomes paramount to underline the importance of searching for the factors that describe the satisfaction of a restaurant customer.

Last, it can be observed that even if the characteristics are perceived as perfect, the customer satisfaction does not reach the maximum. This happens because the model is unable to cover all the variables a customer is taking into consideration. The search for perfect customer satisfaction is not an efficient way to approach the restaurant business industry.

4. Conclusions

The present paper results showed an obvious correlation between food characteristics, restaurant perception and customer satisfaction. The customer satisfaction and restaurant perception are also influenced by demographic (gender) and economic (income) factors. But these characteristics cannot explain the customer behavior in relation to restaurant perception. The regression model is pointing to food taste and food presentation as main sources of customer satisfaction. The fuzzy model presented the interaction between these components and highlighted the importance of correlation between variables. The model predicts satisfaction saturation among restaurant customers.

The proposed research methodology proved to be efficient given the results obtained at each step. The mean difference tests offered relevant information about demographic and economic impact on restaurant perception. The regression model was efficient in choosing the explanatory variables. The fuzzy model offered two main benefits: the modeling of the correlation between variables and the useful visualization of these interactions.

The main drawback of the present paper is given by the small number of parameters taken into consideration: food taste, food smell and food presentation. The methodology proved to be able to deliver relevant information and by adding other parameters like restaurant style and atmosphere, music, service, etc. the model can be improved.

Therefore further research in this area will help to better understand the mechanism behind customer satisfaction.

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COMPUTERIZED MODEL OF RISK MANAGEMENT IN BUSINESS

A. M. TOMA¹, P. MANDU²

Abstract: *Knowing, explaining and interpreting the main types of risks at the level of an organization (micro-risks), but also at the level of national or world economy (macro-risks), requires the correct application of the mathematical models and the correct and well-substantiated formulation of the managerial decisions.*

The occurrence of risk situation and the manager's unawareness of it are serious threats for the organization and its objectives. The manager has to have available, analyze, select and interpret many pieces of information, under stress, before making a decision for avoiding a disaster. Under these circumstances, a computerized model of risk management is the most adequate solution to make the intervention possibilities effective through a quicker and more accurate intervention.

Keywords: *Uncertainty, risk, computerized model, business project, managerial decision*

1. Introduction. Problem enunciation

Risk has been generally associated to an uncertain and probable event or process, which may cause damage, loss, within an economic activity or operation. In this context, there is a broader point of view in terms of risk, for example in business, a risk is when you face an opportunity to win, but that can end with a loss.

Unlike uncertainty, the risk is characterized by the possibility of describing a law (rule) of probability for the expected results, as well as by knowing and valorizing this law, if there is interest. Risk management systematically approaches risk by a series of methods and procedures, which aim at identifying, analyzing and dealing with risks, for an organization.

In this context, there is a wider standpoint, as regards risk; for instance, in the field of business, a situation of risk supposes one's being faced to an earning opportunity, which may end up in a loss [2].

The purpose of any business unfolding in the market-economy system is to obtain profit, which is the positive difference between the earning obtained from selling the products (services) and their cost.

The model proposed, offers enough confidence and a favorable psychological state for managing risk. In accordance with this model, the risk manager processes the information by means of some operational (mathematical) methods and

that favors reaching optimum solutions in the shortest delay, based on some estimated anticipations through a rational model [4].

Under these circumstances, a computerized model of risk management is the most adequate solution to make the intervention possibilities effective through a quicker and more accurate intervention.

2. Schematic of computerized model for Risk Management in business

From Figure 1 it can be deduced that is the principle of operation of the proposed model. There are four levels that will be explained below and which functions as a risk management information system, both vertically and horizontally [6].

3. How the computerized model for Risk Management functions

1. *The manager of the risk situation perceives the danger situation and initiates the computerized system:*

- the danger situation resulted from the action of the risk factors is defined, based on the information provided by the passive system (data and images);

- M.R.S. (the manager of the risk situation) alarms the whole system;

the discriminator of scenarios is transmitted the code of starting a the risk management process.

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Fig. 1. Computerized model of Risk Management in business

2. The simulation (support) unit provides the basic data of the risk situation:

- identifies the typology of risks and defines the essential characteristic features
- foresees the most probable way of dissemination in the system
- defines, assesses the consequences of the risk situation.

3. The active IT department draws up the action strategy of the system as a response to the action of the risk factors:

- based on the initial data provided by the simulation department, the scenario discriminator chooses the most probable scenario which summarizes the integrating action of the risk factors;

- based on a mathematic model, the unit for measuring and evaluating the system risk, measures and evaluates the consequences;
- the strategy generator draws up the strategy for responding to the action of the risk factors, with the support of the logistic department and other internal and external co-workers.

4. The decision maker analyses the strategy provided and implements it through the decisional process:

- The decision content is formulated;
- It is communicated to the implementation department;
- Special measures are implemented for counteracting the action of the risk factors in each department and in the system as a whole;

- results are continuously evaluated, finding the whether the danger state is removed or eliminated.

4. Conclusions

The paper herein is an operational research, for monitoring a situation, based on risk management models. Starting from these theoretical models, we have proved that the risk of profit of a business may be calculated and interpreted.

It proposes a practical model and risk management aim at the correct and well substantiated formulation of the managerial decisions, under risk. On an optimistic perspective, risk is a factor of progress when managed optimally.

Business risk means the probability of gain and loss probability.

The will to take risks is a common element to all managers. Their attitude is, however, different. Some of them are fearful of risks and prefer, therefore, lower risk-generating actions and smaller profits.

Nevertheless, others display risk-attraction behavior and launch in actions with high risks and potential profits.

In business, there is always the risk to lose, which is counterbalanced by the opportunity to earn. This earning opportunity, although it supposes taking risks, drives the businessman in risky enterprises, which may results in significant benefits. With a view to successfully implementing these actions, the earning opportunity and/or the earning volume must exceed the loss probability or volume, because taking risks supposes a significant material motivation [5].

Optimization of the computerized model depends directly on: information collected from the external stimuli in the database; expertise of professionals who draw up the logical frames of various types of adequate scenarios and mathematic models; the viability of the strategies drawn up for preventing, diminishing or annihilating the action of the risk factors;

Using the computerized models of risk management in business is, nowadays and in the future, the most adequate solution for defeating stress and risk taking by the managers;

Risk management with the help of some specialized tools will represent an important support for sustaining the managerial decision in relation with the evolution of internal and external events in the economic and information conflict area.

The efficient utilization of the operational research techniques lead to identifying, evaluating, elaborating the optimal response variants, involved in scientifically forecasting the organizational evolutions, through a proactive, interactive participative-type management.

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FOOD BIODIVERSITY AND PRINCIPAL DIRECTIONS OF RESEARCH IN HEALTH GENERATING GASTRONOMY

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Abstract: *The study proposes an approach of the biounivocal correspondence on the axes „food biodiversity – biotechnological molecular gastronomy”, in a paradigm with consistent theoretical and practical potential in offering culinary products with real qualities, but also attractive and pleasant for the consumers, with the same effects upon health as through supplements under pharmaceutical format. The paper emphasizes a series of results concerning the maximization of the biouse of excellence gastronomic preparations, based on the diversity of incorporated food, with recognized nutritional and therapeutic qualities, but also with hedonic characteristics, scientifically adapting ancient empiric ideas of the oriental feeding manner. The initial result describes the stages of health generating gastronomy biotechnologies and a series if research tracks concerning the maximization of the phytotherapeutic potential of cereal, antocianinic, and mushroom or of animal origin resources. It is finally shaped a conceptual coherence and a large diversification of gastronomic products towards a multifunctional yield: energetic, nutritional, psycho-sensorial, having at the same time a punctual metabolic action of prophylactic type.*

Keywords: *biodiversity, composite food, dishes, gastronomic biotechnologies, health generating gastronomy, hyper complex food.*

1. Introduction

Not being able to live isolated from Nature, biodiversity becomes the complex life network that sustains us all. Protecting biodiversity doesn't only mean to save species or habitats. It also means to assure access at water and food, i.e. all our food deposit is based on biodiversity. Healthy and delicious food, which has been part of Romania and Eastern Europe tradition for a long time, if not accompanied with profound research directions, may be in danger and, together with them, scenery and gastronomic culture, as integrative parts of the identity of these communities.

It is known that 75% from the species of Earth eatable plants have completely disappeared and that 60% from the calorie contribution is ensured only by three cereal species (estimated by FAO). That's why agricultural systems rich in biodiversity that use soil for a sustainable food production (not depending on fossil fuel or pesticides) offer us the best chance to prevent different threats of food procuration chances.

Protecting these systems is important – for our health, for our culture and for leaving the generations to come a richer planet (Gruia, 2010). But all these are not sufficient unless it is taken into consideration the whole of the food act leading towards health generating or „sanogenous” gastronomy.

Thus, the natural Romanian capital, through protected areas and well controlled eco zones, may support the development of activities of creation of food resources for the market (including forest fruit, flavored plants, natural plants for infusions, extracts etc.) that will be able to benefit from the EU policy of quality, including if it will be wisely and correctly used the association with the protected and not polluted zone from which they have been harvested (Gruia, 2011).

In this context we may mention the researcher's preoccupations, that aim at a time horizon for the 2014 – 2020 period, with projections for 2030 – 2050 and perspectives and scenarios for 2100 (Bogdan, A.T and col., 2014). Thus, the Scientific Counsel of the Center of Studies and

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Research in Agrisilvic Biodiversity “Acad. David Davidescu” - C.S.C.B.A.S., from INCE/Romanian Academy, in collaboration with managerial teams of ID project nr. 63258 and ID nr. 77082, has launched the „Project of national, strategic, priority and integrative consensus for the industrial and agro alimentary biochemical development of the European and Euro Atlantic Romania, in the globalised context of the chronic food deficit of mankind” on the 9th of May 2014.

The complexity of the „Food” element may be interpreted as a system with components of high biologic, technical-economic and socio-cultural diversity, characterized by a flow based on an intense dynamics of the draining towards the sustainable procurement of agro-food products (fig.1).

Fig. 1. Systemic flow with basis in biodiversity and focus in health generating gastronomy

It is pointed out the idea that food reflects and is reflected in language, music, poetry and community rituals. These roots are well fixed and often cross with other element roots, entering into contact with different cultures, languages and stories (Culda and Culda, 1995; Gruia, 1996). In essence all these elements constitute a balanced whole. Every product represents a seed, the earth, the culture, the nutrition and the taste, being part of the environment and community sustainability, that make opportune research on the „biodiversity – health generating gastronomy” direction.

In this complexity, rather often it is observed that „because of the trees one does not see the forest”, which in present research imposes the idea to see the general frame in its whole. As a general objective, we propose ourselves exactly analyses of the agro-alimentary system and of its evolution tendencies, in the known difficult tendencies (resource diminishing, climate changes, demographic evolution etc.). We also

propose ourselves to find research directions for health generating gastronomy, that may represent solving elements of what has been previously mentioned.

We will mainly approach, having this paper as a basis, the researches between resource valorization (relatively good biodiversity from Romania in this moment) in relation to the preparation of functional food necessary to the utilization in prototypes of health generating culinary dishes, as elements of a new paradigm.

2. Material and Method

The work methodology imposes to appeal at a series of concepts to sustain the approached problems. Thus, the theory of change of paradigm has at its basis the Einstein paradigm complementarily with the Newton one, theory that represents the conceptual analyses basis in the sense of eMergetic integration of energetic fields, in synergy with intrinsic molecular interaction of the living body, which stands at the

basis of the systemic process of ecoemergent integronics (Gruia, R., 2009). This process explains the coexistence of the systems and the study of their integration process, respectively a form of change of evolutionary and integrative type, of the interrelations between living organisms and their environment, including man's relations with food biodiversity. The pre established resultant is the achievement of something totally new and with the appearance of new properties, of a superior order, as, for example, health generating gastronomy in relation with the relation Environment - Food.

Therefore the new paradigm proposes the integration of a third landing of interest in the so necessary for health production of functional food, respectively of complementary requirements of gastronomic type, centered on the reevaluation of the manner in which there may be assured nutritional, but also therapeutic and hedonic benefits, with their transposition from the household level to the level of the productions of industrial type (Gruia, 2008).

Thus, there are taken into consideration methodological landings of the change of paradigm in the integrated system „Environment-Food biodiversity-Processing-Dishes”, with finality towards health generating gastronomy.

3. Results and Discussions

In applied biology it is known the Newtonian model of molecular interaction and, of course, the fact that the model is mainly based on the idea that organism is considered as a mechanism controlled by the brain and the peripheral nervous system. Another perspective is offered by the model of Einstein paradigm. The Einstein paradigm, with applications in biology and especially in medicine, concentrates on energetic-subtle fields that are at the origin of the physic body, but also contribute at its functioning, placing on another inferior plan the molecular interaction, approached by the Newtonian paradigm (Gruia, 2011).

The application of the mentioned models at conditions linked to continuous growth of the level of ambient factors that cause biotic and abiotic stress sustains and motivates the demand of products from the functional food category (Doug, 2006; Maleta, 2007; Koepler et al, 2012; Kabir et al, 2013). These ones, together with basic nutritional characteristics, may prevent illness appearance, metabolic diseases, by the content in natural bioactive compounds with

relevant level of health generating efficiency. (Swami, 2005, Mitmesser, 2007; Sahdeo et al, 2009; Coll et al 2010; Sandeep et al, 2011). The tendency to satisfy health necessities by nutritional contribution has a still little valorized potential in the situation when functional food is not also integrated in composite food of gastronomic type, i.e. hyper complex food. Thus, we speak about prevention and especially about complementarities and even an optimal alternative face to allopathic medication of synthesis, often associated to undesirable secondary effects.

Concepts and advanced research in the production of functional food of the last decade have mainly concretized on two interest landings:

- Frontier science progresses (metabolomics, nutrigenomics, transcriptomics, proteomics etc.) in decoding interaction mechanisms at molecular level of bioactive compounds, emphasizing cell structures implied in defensive mechanisms of the human body face to ambient provocations.
- Innovative development of advanced technologies of division and concentration of active principles with health generating potential, in sparing conditions, not to affect natural active stereo structures, as well as their integration on natural synergic supports under the aspect of therapeutic relevance.

We mention that, even though these researches have allowed a better knowing and integration of the bioactive health generating compounds in products and preparations, the level of effective bio use of these preparations is to be discussed in many cases. This vulnerability of the present products of alimentary origin, referring to the level of real biological utility, may be also perceived under the aspect of neglecting sensorial characteristics, directly correlated to the level of acceptance of alimentary products by receptors situated at the level of the gastro intestinal tract.

To this end it must be mentioned the fact that digestive enzyme production, through which is ensured a high level of bio use, presupposes sensorial characteristics of attractive taste, smell and flavor, and these indispensable qualities in the good functioning of metabolic processes impose a complementary approach of gastronomic type.

On the other hand, in an approach to Orient of a holistic type (Ma and Fa ming, 2007), the gastronomic dimension of the food products used for therapeutic purposes is perceived as an essential element. This aspect has yet been less

taken into consideration up to now, as a factor of real metabolic efficiency in the production of functional food. This real capacity, at which attractiveness of gastronomic type is added, may orient research directions.

In this case, in order to effectively act in the direction to obtain benefits for health, a piece of food should present, next to its relevant nutritional component (which may be logistically projected) also characteristics of a sensorial order, under the aspect of taste, smell and, eventually, color, in order to satisfy at an optimum level the potential consumers' sensorial

preferences, by inducing hedonic effects of "taste pleasure stimulation" and consequently stimulate the enzymatic production of acidic digestive fluid.

Synthesizing the described high complexity aspects, the research/innovation flow in the field of health generating gastronomic biotechnologies, as a conceptual forerunner for technologic flows, we consider it to be characterized by the next principle steps from figure 2.

Fig. 2. Conceptual and operational stages in research directions from health generating gastronomic biotechnologies

In order to achieve such a dynamics (according to fig.2) there are necessary orientations concerning the action directions. From the numerous present preoccupations, in our opinion there may be solved a series of older or newer aspects, that represent at the same time directions of alimentary and gastronomic research in the field of bio-economy too: - optimization of gastronomic type of cereal resources; - optimization of gastronomic type of antocianinic resources; - optimization through gastronomic processing of alimentary and/or therapeutic mushrooms, and, in parallel, optimization of gastronomic type of animal resources.

3.1. Directions of research in the biotechnologies of health generating gastronomy

Direction 1 – Research concerning maximization of phyto therapeutic and nutritional potential of cereal resources through optimization of gastronomic type.

Phyto therapeutic potential of different cereal species has been indicating since ancient times the cereal consumption with specificity for differentiated treatments (respectively, mush, decoction, porridge, for products roasted and/or fried in oils etc.) (Tuluca et al 1998; Drownowski and Gomez, 2000; King and Gabriel, 2007; Jin and Hayek, 2013; Kontogianni et al 2013). Known as basic nutritional products in satisfying

metabolic demands (carbohydrates with slow absorption, cereal proteins, mineral macro and micronutrients, soluble and insoluble dietetic fibers), present research have also given points to health generating characteristics of certain cereals, as a substratum of prevention and/or counteracting of certain sickening with diversified health generating effect, as, for example:

- Oat: sustainer of general nervous tonus, anti depressive, anti stress, remedy for certain skin affections;
- Wheat: emollient, laxative, cardio-vascular tonic, respiratory and renal tonic;
- Maize: anti inflammatory, diuretic, reduces nervous excitability, laxative, regenerator, recommended in arthritis, diabetes;
- Rye: constipation, renal, cardio vascular illnesses, hypertension, retarding aging phenomena, atherosclerosis, remineralizer.

Phyto therapeutic potential of different cereal species is correlated with gastronomic practices, different procedures of preparation applied in the Orient, indicating since ancient times cereal consumption, with specificity for differentiated treatment, respectively mush, decoction, porridge, paste for products roasted and/or fried in oils etc.

The health generating contribution to increase the level of bio use aims to present enzymatic treatment with phytases, in order to minimize the level of phytic acid existing in variable quantities in the outer cover of cereal grains, responsible with content minimizing in macro and micro bio gene elements: calcium, magnesium, iron, copper, manganese, zinc etc. Through enzymatic hydrolyze of phytic acid in moderate acid environment, anterior to the preparation of different products, this risk is diminished (Lowenstein, 1969).

Globbered cereals for breakfast may also be added with synergic natural compounds, under the aspect of maximizing the therapeutic potential, before globbing through mixture integration, or after globbing by covering the surface with relevant, natural products, in order to increase nutraceutic density. This type of processing also offers a large opportunity for the application of selective gastronomic processing.

Otherwise, there may be achieved different functional cereal sorts, nutritionally balanced, preferring with supplements of pressed at cold oils of triglyceride type, with a relevant content of mono or poly non saturated fat acids, respectively with a high content of Omega 3 and

Omega 6. In different bakery and pastry products, both to increase phyto therapeutic potential and to intensify sensorial characteristics and to protect against microbes, there may be added essential flavoring oils, as such, macerated, hydrophilic or lipophilic of spices or flavoring vegetal extracts.

The cereal basis may constitute a preferential substratum of application of innovative gastronomic products through integration, respectively prototyping different mixtures, by obtaining preparations from the category of salted or sweet snacks, respectively different composite dishes.

To integrate a number of resources detaining active principles, flavoring as such, under the form of concentrated extracts, may confer an extremely diversified psycho sensorial potential. There are taken into account traditional flavoring resources as such, or their mixture, to synergically shape a large variety of gastronomic recipes of the "Haute gastronomie" type with a large synergy in intensifying hedonic characteristics. As potential resources to flavor there may be enumerated the following ones, with differentiate utilizations for sweet or salted cereal products: pepper, ginger, cloves, cinnamon, fennel, curcuma, cumin, anise, cardamom, nutmeg, extracted concentrated from conifers, fir and pine tree buds, rosemary, extracts from flavor plants, as, for example Melissa, Basil, mint, Sage, lavender, oregano, thyme, dill, lovage etc.

Under the aspect of the implication of advanced technologies, it is nowadays also practiced to micronize integral cereal grains at the level of nano particles (10–12). To micronize eases to release secondary bioactive metabolites under powder form, as, for example, strong antioxidant phenol carboxylic (ferulic, paracumaric etc.)

Direction 2 – Research concerning maximization of phyto therapeutic and sensorial potential of certain food products based on antocianinic resources, by optimization of gastronomic type .

Antocianinic resources, mainly represented by fruit and flowers intensely colored in nuances of violet red, respectively glycosidase forms of certain aglicons (as for example pelargonidin, petunidin, delphinidin, malvidin, cianidin etc.), present many therapeutic characteristics, are strongly antioxidant, protect the heart and blood vessels with a relevant impact in the bio protection of the lipophilic cell membranes, especially at the brain level, being in present perceived as stimulators of the cognitive and

memory capacities, and last but not least, as retina photo protectors (Kim et al, 2010; Rachad et al, 2012).

The present technologic contribution is represented by athermal extraction, through processing with pectolitic enzymes that favor the splitting of gelling heteropoliozes, with release of bigger quantities of cell juice from the organic matrix. In our laboratories is also practiced the advanced extraction in subcritical regime, at maximum 35 – 40°C, with ecologic freon (solvent HCF-134a), in order to increase the concentration in active substances.

It is to be mentioned that recently ((Eidenberger, 2013) have also been identified methods of color stabilization, having in view that antocianinic extracts are stable as such only at pH values in moderate acid environment, rather under the value of 4,5 pH units. Through supplements of molecular constituents detaining sulphur hydric (-SH) as, for example: N-acetilcistein or glutation, there are formed stable colored complexes at higher pH values, respectively at average values and even in moderate alkaline environment, with extension through emulsification in lipophilic environment too.

From the point of view of gastronomic optimization, it is completely possible a complementary approach through adding agro flavor natural extracts from spicy resources, as, for example: extracts from cloves, nutmeg, cardamom, coriander etc., or through foliar macerated supplements from flavored plants, as, for example: Basil, Melissa, lavender, jasmine etc., or from conifers, pine and fir tree buds, rosemary etc. From previous research we have observed that mentioned extracts may be added in variable proportions, generally at levels of 0,5 - 2,5%.

Next to flavoring characteristics, the mentioned extracts present a high antioxidant, antibacterial, antifungicide, antiviral etc. capacity, mentioning the fact that adding certain terpenoid concentrates, in conformity with recent discoveries, stimulates carbohydrate and lipid metabolism, facilitating the weight loss (Zijia et al, 2009; Tsuyoshi and Noboyuki, 2010).

As a consequence, antocianinic resources that up to present constitute the bases of the obtaining of certain traditional products (syrups, jams, preserves) may constitute an objective of innovative gastronomic research in order to obtain functional food sorts with maximized health generating and hedonic potential.

Direction 3 – Research concerning the optimization of metabolic efficiency of alimentary and/or therapeutic mushrooms, through gastronomic processing.

Natural flavoring extracts in the different sorts of mushrooms as such, may be correlated with gastronomic practices. Mentioned as having remarkable health generating characteristics, superior basidiomicetes, but also spawn products derived from these ones, through cultivation in automatic bioreactors, present differentiated therapeutic characteristics for preventing and treating numerous affections (Qi Y and Sun, 2012; Bartunek and Bard, 2012).

There must be mentioned the capacity to influence the host (the human body) in the direction of strengthening the own capacity of defense face to harmful ambient factors of biotic or abiotic type.

In the present mushrooms are considered as being situated at “PHARMA-NUTRITION” interface, in conformity with certain recent studies (Leal et al, 2013).

With a high potential of imunomodulation, especially due to polisugar hydrophilic structures of α and β glucanic and proteogluconic type, the mushrooms extracts present health generating relevance in lipophilic environment too, being anti-inflammatory, anti-cholesterol, anti-hyperglycemic, anti-obesity, antihistaminic, anti-cancer etc.

To the fore is also situated the specific capacity to flavor a number of mushrooms cultivated at industrial scale, but especially certain species coming from spontaneous micro flora. The extracts or preparations from these mushrooms have constituted themselves over the time as genuine detainers of “high gastronomic potential”, aspect extended in the present through biotechnologies of advanced cultivation.

Different mushrooms, mainly for alimentary purposes, and less mushrooms with preponderant therapeutic potential, lend themselves to the obtaining of alimentary preparations of “Haute gastronomie” type, through integration in nutritional and/or spicy substrata, as, for example, pastry and meat products, mixtures with cereals (rice), pasta, oily soaks with additive extras in different “dressings” etc.

Taking into consideration both health generating characteristics and appetizing flavors, mushrooms confer a number of opportunities to diversify and implement innovative gastronomy, perceived as a component of the new paradigm.

In perspective, it must be mentioned that mushroom processing may be the beneficiary of certain advanced extraction procedures and, later on, of drying on powder supports of maltodextrine or cito protective proteins. Also, powder products with high solubility may constitute a basis for the obtaining of certain tonic drinks, added with spicy flavors. Certain preliminary data show that different extracts of mushrooms may be integrated in receipts of composite food, with immune modulation potential.

Direction 4 – Research concerning metabolic equilibrium through optimization of gastronomic type of animal resources.

Since ancient times, products of animal origin have been perceived as essential elements in health maintaining, but also as remedies in the treatment of different affections, as, for example: pork or mutton and liver constitute a general tonic, improve the sight or constitute a remedy in certain blood illnesses, beef has a positive action at muscle and bone level and may successfully treat edema, lamb influences birth and is efficient in stagger curing etc.

During the last years, the therapeutic problem through components of animal origin strongly reappear, better known being the research linked to taurine (a betasulphonate amino acid: $\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-SO}_3\text{H}$), or to fish protein extracts.

Taurine has a high antioxidant potential and prevents cell death. It has a significant bio protective effect in inflammation stopping, in improving cardio-vascular illnesses and neuronal affections. It is involved in the formation of photoreceptor stratus. At mammals it is abundantly found in tissues, in skeletal muscles, heart, liver, kidneys and brain. Besides the fact that it has known anti obese, anti hyperglycemic and of attenuation of Metabolic Syndrome dysfunctions (doses of 0,3-3 %) characteristics, taurine has the osmoregulating capacity to stabilize cell membrans, to control the blood pressure. It regulates the concentration of intracellular bivalent calcium (Ca^{2+}), the taurine being in fact found in extracellular cells. This amino acid practically regulates the ion concentration in blood and the neuro transmitters (Chuan et al, 2014).

Recent research show stringent needs of the organism as for resources of animal origin, even since birth, taking into account the fact that maternal milk contains taurine (40 micro molls) which stimulates oxide reductive reactions that take place in the tricarboxilic acid (cycle TCA or

Krebs or Szent-Gyorgyi-Krebs) (Krebs and Weitzman, 1987). There is influenced the production of glutationperoxidasis, glutationreductasis and superoxidismutasis enzymes, having as a result anti inflammatory effects. That is why, in case children are fed with soja milk, the taurine supplement becomes compulsory.

The Extract of fish protein is obtained from lean fish, such as cod fish, black cod fish and aiglefin. In order to obtain short polypeptidic chains and with small molecular weight, this extracts is obtained by enzymatic hydrolyze in soft pH and temperature conditions. To guarantee an optimal quality, the process is strictly controlled so that to preserve amino acids (starting with raw material) and to improve bio availability and solubility of the protein proposing two types of protein extracts from fish: in powder and in solution.

3.2. Place and role of the biotechnology of health generating gastronomy

It is known that, starting with 2014, there has been established an inter-sectorial public policy that may join public intervention in agro-food system to public health and immaterial patrimony. This fact would offer a meaning to an overview public policy on the bio economy line, which, on one hand, supports agriculture in order to offer raw material necessary for food, in conformity with CAP, but, on the other hand, would also survey what population consumes and which is the effect upon its health, through the gastronomic model.

The systemic flow, with its basis in biodiversity and focus in health generating gastronomy (according to fig.1), shaped in conceptual and operational stages in research directions of the biotechnologies of health generating gastronomy (according to fig.2), lead (in this moment) to a series of research directions that we group in 4 general programs: - optimizing of gastronomic type of cereal resources; - optimizing of gastronomic type of antocianinic resources; - optimizing through gastronomic processing of alimentary and/or therapeutic mushrooms; - optimizing of gastronomic type of animal resources. Therefore, the present paper has an important continuity element, opening in fact the research field of the third pylon of the alimentary act (after agricultural engineering and food engineering), i.e. gastronomic engineering.

In the dynamics of the alimentary act, gastronomic engineering has at least the same importance as food agriculture and industry, but for sure it has the largest complexity, because, besides the science and technology of culinary production, we speak about the impact upon body health, about gastronomic culture and even about immaterial aspects of philosophy and spirituality. Concretizing, we may observe that health generating gastronomy is based on 4 important pylons, having as resources: - cereals, - fruit and flowers, - mushroom and - animal resources. Thus, gastronomic biotechnologies are actually applied to all kingdoms with economic importance, aiming to health and food safety. The biotechnologies of health generating gastronomy become thus an important branch of bio economy.

Conclusions

The approach of gastronomic type to the interface between environment (biodiversity) and food is sustained, as a new paradigm, by advanced nutritional sciences and culinary art, as a basis of life quality, respectively of health and "well-being", scientifically underlying molecular mechanisms of bioactive nutrient contribution and their processing with sparing biotechnical methods.

The 3 conceptual and operational stages lead to the bio use maximization, the metabolic optimization of basic nutritional products and of trofins, under the conditions of satisfying hedonic attributes, consolidating the work methodology in the biotechnology of health generating gastronomy.

There appear directions that may constitute an objective of innovative gastronomic research in order to obtain hyper complexe foods with functional composite alimentary sorts, as well as with maximized health generating and hedonic potential. The gastronomic dimension of food products used for therapeutic purposes is perceived as an essential element, but less taken into consideration up to now, as a factor of real metabolic efficiency in the production of functional food.

In the complex frame of bio economy there may be distinguished the branch of the gastronomic biotechnology, with molecular thoroughgoing study, aiming to obtain benefits for health. Thus, it can analyze the hyper complex food (dishes etc.), along with the relevant nutritional component supported by food

biodiversity, who presents characteristics of composite type and culinary constructivism. Can be highlighted order sensory terms of teste odor and color, with potential induction of a hedonic type of „stimulating the pleasure of taste” with the effect upon enzymatic production of acidic digestive fluid, concomitantly with metabolic regulation and balance.

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SURVEY REGARDING THE LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE OF ROMANIAN CONSUMERS TOWARDS FOOD LABELING - SHORT ANALYSES IN THE FRAME OF IRSES 318946 PROJECT

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Abstract: *The aim of the presented paper is to find out the consumer level of knowledge in the area of nutritional labeling. The survey was used during 2013-2015, having as subjects 200 consumers from Central Romania. The analyses show that list of ingredients is very important in a proportion of 73%. 84% of consumers think that the list of substances causing allergies is very important, 10% say it is very important and 6% consider less important this issue.*

The study showed that 75% of respondents feel that are well and very well informed about nutrition labels. However the same consumers give importance to nutritional information's in a rate of only 36%. Also, the same consumers have deficiencies in understanding certain words on food labels.

Keywords: *survey, technological development, energy value, allergy;*

1. Introduction

In recent decades, one of the essential problems of manufacturing companies is the knowledge of the manner in which they respond to various stimuli that consumers will use to achieve their final goal, profit as possible.

Studying consumer behavior became a concern of marketers, as they can learn how buyers choose their goods and services to satisfy their many needs, and which factors influence their choice.

The increasing complexity of economic life, has led to knowledge of human economic behavior mechanism that is becoming larger and more complicated, requiring separate study of two intrinsic components: human behavior as producer of goods and services and as consumer. Given the considerable diversification of supply, consumers have wide choices [6], [7].

On the other hand, increasing purchasing power, while raising the level of education and culture, it enables the buyer to satisfy as many needs, more sophisticated level of quality, higher aspects, of who the manufacturer is obliged to take into account, in order to meet the wishes of the consumer [1], [2].

If the manufacturer does not expound these new options of the client, he will move to another producer.

Current concerns manifested in the European Union related to food safety and security, and traceability of food products, has generated a specific legislation on their quality by specific regulations for the following categories: nutrition labeling designation of origin, traditional specialty guaranteed (TSG), protected geographical indication (PGI) [4].

The purpose of food labeling is to guarantee consumer access to complete information, on the content, and composition of products, to protect the health and interests.

Further information can provide details about a specific product feature, such as origin or manufacturing process. Some foods such as genetically modified organisms, allergenic foods and products intended for infants or even various beverages are also covered by specific regulations [8].

With technological developments in food industries, labeling should be as complete because the consumer has to be informed about the product when buying.

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2. Materials and methods

The main goal of this project was to understand consumers, to know their level of knowledge and to improve certain existing problems.

In this manner it was used a questionnaire of 7 questions, and respondents were chosen from rural and urban areas of Brasov County [3].

To achieve this goal there have been set a number of other secondary objectives:

1. Estimated percentage of the level of knowledge held by the consumer to enable understanding of the information content on food labels;

2. Assessing the understanding level of compulsory elements that appear on a food label;

3. Collecting data about age, work place, gender, monthly income, etc.

To achieve these objectives there were set a number of activities such as drawing up a questionnaire with 7 questions, to be completed by a representative sample of consumers in Brasov County [5]. The questions and objectives

no. 1, 2, 3 and 6 were focused on the behavior of the consumer regarding food labeling [5], and the remained questions no. 4, 5 and 7 present the level of knowledge of the respondent consumers, and will be presented as following.

For the fulfillment of the 1st target, estimation the percentage of knowledge level held by the consumer that would render the content information on food labels, consumers will respond to the question *"Appreciate the knowledge that you have, that allows you to understand the content of information on food labels, especially regarding food intake matched to your health "*, with a numbers from 1 to 10, with 1 being the sole discretion note negative.

For the 2nd objective, assess the degree of understanding of mandatory elements that appear on the food label, consumers will respond to the question: *"To what extent you understand a food product label claims"*, consumer response will be given by selecting the corresponding items in Table 1.

Table 1. Level of understanding food label claims

Label claims	Very easy	Easy	Difficult	Do not understand
List of ingredients				
Energy value (calories, kJ)				
Proteins				
Lipids				
Cholesterol				
Carbohydrates				
Fibers				
Vitamins				
Sodium/salt				
Mineral substances				
Recommended daily dose				
Nutritional value (calories, proteins) per portion				

It is accepted only one choice for each item of food label.

For clear results it is necessary that the sample of consumers interviewed to be representative for the county of Brasov. To assess this issue, consumers need to complete the questionnaire with general information on gender, age, level of education, residence, monthly income, number of dependent children, job and marital status.

3. Results and discussions

For the 4th question, *"Give marks from 1 to 10 for the level of knowledge that you have, that allows you to understand the information content of food labels"* the results are presented in fig.1.

Fig.1. Question no. 4, Level of knowledge

The study showed that 75% of respondents feel well and very well informed about nutrition labels. If a consumer does not know to distinguish between 2 food products, the choice is made by the most convenient alternative, price. This can lead to counterfeit products. People have a comprehensive view of what is generally "ecologic" but are not familiar with the more specific issues, like organic farming, processing of products and certification systems. Those who

are more familiar with the aspects of organic food and production are expected to show a more favorable behavior, well-defined and consistently to these products. Studies show that less than 50% of europeans considered themselves confident and sufficiently well informed as consumers.

For question number 5, "To what extent you understand the claims in food labeling", the results are presented in the following graphics a-m.

Fig. 2. Question no. 5 from the questionnaire
 a. – Level of understandig the list of ingredients
 b. - Level of understandig the energy value

94% understand very easy and easy the list of ingredients, but 6% have difficulties understanding certain aspects.

The results of the questionnaire are good, seeing a growing trend in the level of information held by clients. Consumers can easily understand the labeling of products that they buy. Every day

we are enslaved by all kind of advertisements appealing to juice, biscuits, chips. These processed foods containing additives and artificial colors have the element 'tag' in common.

Consumers accord importance to this issue, because the problem of gaining weight is increasingly present in society. Its consequences

lead to low self-esteem and serious health problems. All this could be avoided through attention to packaging.

94% of respondents understand very easy and easy the concept of energy mentioned on food labels.

Fig. 3. Question no. 5 from the questionnaire
 c.- Level of understandig the protein mention from labels
 d. - Level of understandig the lipid mention from labels

58% of respondents understand easily the term protein, mostly women and recognizing that prefer high protein diets. "I like high protein diets because it helps me loose weight and are relatively easy to hold", says Maria, 27 years old.

Consumers understand very easily the term fat (56%) and know the difference between healthy fats and harmful to the human body.

As the essential fatty acids Omega 3 and Omega 6 can not be synthesized in the body, consumers take care to incorporate these unsaturated fats in the daily diet.

Fig. 4. Question no. 5 from the questionnaire
 e. – Level of understandig the cholesterol term from labels
 f. - Level of understandig the carbohydrates term from labels

46% of respondents know the term cholesterol as a fat that is found in almost all animal origin food, but never in the vegetal ones.

Consumers between the ages of 25 to 60 give great importance to food products rich in animal fats, because the amount of harmful cholesterol

increases, it deposits on the blood vessels and causes narrowing of the arteries.

More and more people try to choose a healthy diet, with products rich in fiber.

Fig. 5. Question no. 5 from the questionnaire
 g. – Level of understandig the fiber term from labels
 h. - Level of understandig the vitamin mentions from labels

86% of consumers understand easy and very easy the term of carbohydrates, while 12% find it difficult to understand this concept.

Fig. 6. Question no. 5 from the questionnaire
 i. – Level of understandig the salt mention from labels
 j - Level of understandig the mineral substances term from labels

50% of respondents understand easily the term minerals, while 10% find it difficult to understand and recognize this term.

Consumers between 40-60 years consume foods rich in selenium; a rich diet of this mineral significantly boosts their mood, feeling more confident and energetic.

A growing number of people interested in maintaining and improving health use supplements for this purpose. Vitamins with minerals, once in the body, are assimilated and

used each individually, in various chemical reactions for normal metabolic processes.

The mineral elements, called bio-elements are essential to proper functioning of various organs and systems, mostly involved in metabolism, water balance in the body, bone health, central nervous system, and the immune system.

Sodium concept is very easy and understandable and recognized by 92% of our survey respondents. Salt is criminalized in recent years for its adverse effects on health but in

moderation plays a key role in developing the muscles and nervous system.

Fig.7. Question no. 5 from the questionnaire

k. – Level of understandig the recomended daily dose mention from labels
l. – Level of understandig the special mentions from labels

Nutritional value

Fig. 8. Question no. 5 from the questionnaire

m. - Level of understandig the nutritional value term from labels

54% of consumers understand the concept of recommended daily dose, special mentions on food labels and nutritional value of food.

For the 7th point, consumers have to complete the survey with personal data:

- Gender;
- Age;
- Level of education;
- Residence;
- Children in support;
- Monthly income;
- Work place;
- Marital staus.

Fig. 11. Question no. 7 from the questionnaire
 e. – Informations about the number of children in support
 f. – Informations about the monthly income

Fig. 12. Question no. 7 from the questionnaire
 g. – Informations regarding the work place
 h.- Informations about marital status

People between 40-60 years believe that it is very important to know in what conditions the food products were processed, packaged and stored. Regarding the young consumers and their lifestyle, is observed that the main cause of illness is the unhealthy lifestyles.

Followed by inactivity unbalanced diet, smoking, alcohol consumption are the major factors that have a role in the emergence of chronic diseases. Despite the large number of young people informed about the effects of lifestyle on health, most continue to have the same habits that will negatively influence health.

" I consumer fast food even though I know it is not healthy ", says Andrew (23 years)

Conclusions

Of the 200 respondents who answered the questionnaires in Braşov, the **list of ingredients** is very important in a proportion of **73%**, considering also that the **health recommendations** are very important **52%**.

84% of consumers think that the list of substances causing allergies is **very important**, **10%** say it is **very important** and **6%** consider **less important** this issue.

The study showed that **75%** of respondents feel that are **well and very well informed** about nutrition labels.

However the same consumers give importance to nutritional information's in a rate of only **36%**. Also, the same consumers have deficiencies in understanding certain words on food labels.

The final results show that in order to understand and realise the informations from labels, the costumers need to be educated regarding labeling and healthy diet. This is a duty for educators (Universities, high schools, etc) and for members of civic society (NGO's, other associations).

Neverthelese it is a duty of each parent to assure a healthy diet for their family.

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GEOTOURISTIC STUDY REGARDING IDENTIFICATION OF RESOURCES WITH GASTRONOMIC PROFILE FROM SOUTHERN DOBROGEA AND OPPORTUNITY OF THEIR RECOVERY

M. POPESCU¹ R. GRUIA²

Abstract: *This study aims that the combination of local traditions with other touristic resources to highlight a number of polyvalent touristic routes who can contribute on bioeconomy direction to social and multicultural development of rural area from Southern Dobrogea, by capitalizing of gastro-tourism as part a sustainable agri-tourism. Observations of this study shows that being a multicultural geographical area, the local cuisine of ethnically diverse population constitutes the main element of specific for finding solutions of touristic attraction based on diversity and complementarity. Ethno-gastronomic particularities are directly proportional to the ethnic density. Thus, according to the dominance of ethnic groups within rural settlements will be highlighted a touristic regionalization with gastronomic profile in area of research. To describe solutions starting from geotouristic diagnosis, necessary to define the touristic specific with gastronomic profile from Southern Dobrogea, and identify mechanisms of efficiency for integrating in agri-touristic circuit and rural tourism of optimized valences in this area.*

Keywords: *Dobrogea, gastronomy, multicultural geographic area, sustainable tourism*

1. Introduction

The traditional cuisine that valuable items related to a particular way of preparing food have been preserved over the centuries must be known and appreciated. For agri-tourism, this represents a particularly valuable resource and full tasted of tourists of country houses. For needs of agri-tourism to be developed specific food premises, representative, where to offer traditional dishes in a pleasant setting, complementary with elements of culture, appropriate architecture, specific interior and exterior decorations [4]. In dining spaces can be organized artistic programs, which offers more attractive of food service. A way to promote of agri-tourism is organizing meals on certain touristic routes, with traditional cuisine and wine tasting, fruits or other specific foods, occasion to be distributed flyers with area's presentation and possibilities of agri-tourism practicing like the type developed in the mountain area [9,10,11,3].

The whole Southern Dobrogea is a plateau unit and it is a territorial system well highlighted. By its geographical position, between Danube and Black Sea Coast, Southern Dobrogea has a

diversified touristic potential offered by the contrast of natural environment, cultural sights and local traditions [1]. Southern Dobrogea has an ethnic and confessional diversity, being an interference territory between cultures and behaviors: Western and Eastern, Christian and Muslim, Latin and Slavic [12].

Folk, ethnic, cultural, ecological, gastronomic traditions from rural area and features of local environment are insufficiently for development of tourism, for jobs, for generating income and ensuring a positive impact on the sense of dignity and pride of the local communities [5]. Through innovative actions for the enhancement of local heritage can be achieved increasing the attractiveness of rural areas for both, rural population and tourists. Better recognition and protection of cultural and natural heritage would lead to further identify the rural population with its living areas and their desire to remain in rural areas, thus reducing the desire to migrate to urban areas. There are development alternatives of bioeconomy on trend of green economy and food-tourism profile [2,7,8].

The ethnic diversity of Southern Dobrogea is enhanced by the presence of non-native

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communities, which are mainly inhabited villages or in part, bring their specificity: Turks, Tatars,

In this multicultural geographical area, the local cuisine of diverse ethnic population from Southern Dobrogea is the main element of specificity for finding solutions of touristic attraction based on diversity and complementarity, as research method. Expected solutions can be capitalized as original touristic products and programs, such as the direction of ethno-gastronomy [6].

The overall aim of this paper is to define the touristic specific with gastronomic profile from Southern Dobrogea and identify solutions of integration in the agri-tourism circuit, in order to sustainable development of rural tourism in this area. The specific aims are related to identification, structuring and optimization of concrete geotouristic resources, in order to highlight the polyvalence and effectiveness increase tourism of studied area.

2. Material and Method

The research methodology consists of bibliographic documentation, and field research to identify villages where ethnic groups have a

Aromanians, Lippovans, but also in cities that had or have ethnic cosmopolitan structures [13]. majority share, with specific customs and traditions, mapping with regionalization of local gastronomic resources and opportunities of touristic valorization. In this way is used the thematic mapping [16] of Southern Dobrogea territory. Then it processes the information through comparative analysis methods of maps [14], by statistical aspects and overlay maps techniques to establish networks and nodes to optimization of routes and touristic programs.

3. Results and discussions

Southern Dobrogea territory has been inhabited since ancient times [12]. At the census of 2011 year, Southern Dobrogea counted over 640,000 inhabitants living in 8 cities and 138 villages, grouped into 36 communes [15]. Southern Dobrogea is a geographical multicultural area, full of nature and history [1], where together with Romanians (82.9%) live Turks and Tatars (6.2%), Russian-Lippovans (0.6%), Aromanians (2.4%), Roma (1.2%), and others nationalities (6.7%) (table 1).

Table 1 Southern Dobrogea - The ethnic structure of the population, on life areas (processing datas, [15])

Human settlements	Population (inhabitants)	Romanians (%)	Aromanians (%)	Russian Lippovans (%)	Turks and Tatars (%)	Roma (%)	Other (%)
Urban area	461,319	82.4	2.9	0.3	6.1	1.1	7.2
Rural area	179,052	84.4	1.3	1.2	6.3	1.6	5.2
Southern Dobrogea	640,371	82.9	2.4	0.6	6.2	1.2	6.7

On life areas, the ethnic structure is quite similar, except that more Aromanians living in urban areas (Constanta, Ovidiu, Techirghiol) and more Russian- Lippovans living in rural areas (Ghindărești, Limanu).

The multicultural of this area, as a separate specific, it is outlined of the main communities weight in the **ethnic structure** of the administrative units is shown in figure 1.

It appears that the largest weight in area of research have **Turks and Tatars**, well represented, with values above average in urban area (Băneasa - 21.1%, Medgidia - 16.5%, Techirghiol - 15.1%, Mangalia - 7.3%, Murfatlar - 6.5%), and in rural area (Dobromir - 57.8%, Independența - 21.2%, Cobadin - 16.6%,

Castelu - 13.6%, Amzacea - 13.5%, Ciocârlia - 11.8%, Valu lui Traian - 11.4%, Comana - 9.3%, 23 August - 8.3%, Mereni - 8.2%, Agigea - 7.6%, Tuzla - 6.9%, Topraisar - 6.8%, Lipnița - 6.6%).

Aromanians are better represented in the North-Eastern part of region, in the metropolitan area of Constanța, the representative human settlements of this community are Mihail Kogălniceanu (13%) and Ovidiu (7%).

Russian-Lippovans are more concentrated in Northern Dobrogea, but in area of research, Ghindărești village is the example with a majority population of almost 95%.

According to ethnic and confessional criteria, morpho-structural differences and physiognomy can identify villages belonging to majority ethnic

community in the settlement (Turkish, Tatar, Lippovans, Aromanians), with various aspects of specific ethnic daily life, which customizes them [12].

Fig. 1. Southern Dobrogea - the ethnic diversity

By processing datas it can be seen in synthesis Southern Dobrogea in terms of ethnicity, and in table, the geotouristic situation existing in therefore multicultural.

Table 2 Southern Dobrogea - The weight of main ethnic groups, in human settlements (processing datas, [15])

The weight	Aromanians (%)	Russian-Lippovans (%)	Turks and tatars (%)
> 50.0%	-	Ghindărești - 94.5%	Dobromir - 57.8%
20.1% - 50.0%	-	-	Independența - 21.2% Băneasa - 21.1%
10.1% - 20.0%	M. Kogălniceanu - 13.0%	-	Cobadin - 16.6% Medgidia - 16.5% Techirghiol - 15.1% Castelu - 13.6% Amzacea - 13.5% Ciocârlia - 11.8% Valu lui Traian - 11.4%
5.1% - 10.0%	Ovidiu - 7.0%	-	Comana - 9.3% 23 August - 8.3% Mereni - 8.2% Agigea - 7.6% Mangalia - 7.3% Tuzla - 6.9% Topraisar - 6.8% Lipnița - 6.6% Murfatlar - 6.5%

			Eforie - 5.8% Cumpăna - 5.5% Ovidiu - 5.5%
1.0% - 5.0%	Constanța - 4.0% Techirghiol - 3.0% Cobadin - 2.3% Castelu - 2.2% Lumina - 2.2% Cumpăna - 1.4% Medgidia - 1.3% Poarta Albă - 1.3% Agigea - 1.1% Valu lui Traian - 1.0%	Limanu - 2.8% Năvodari - 1.7%	Constanța - 4.9% Lumina - 4.1% M. Kogălniceanu - 3.8% Pecineaga - 3.5% Limanu - 3.0% Cernavodă - 2.8% Siliștea - 2.7% Albești - 2.6% Ion Corvin - 2.5% Adamclisi - 2.1% Bărăganu - 1.9% Deleni - 1.8% Negru Vodă - 1.6% Poarta Albă - 1.5% Năvodari - 1.2%

Also, Southern Dobrogea has a diversified **touristic potential**: Black Sea Coast, lakes along Sea and Danube, protected areas, monasteries, historical sites, museums, traditional folk art,

villages with Dobrogea's specific [14]. In figure 2 are mapped cultural and touristic sights from Southern Dobrogea.

Fig. 2. Southern Dobrogea - cultural touristic resources

Direct or indirect it's observed that the **traditional gastronomy** is a complementary component for rural tourism with cultural specific. Representative in rural areas are village's museums from Mihail Kogălniceanu, Limanu, Topalu, the Monument of Adamclisi, Dervent (Ostrov) and "Sf. Andrei" Cave (Ion Corvin) Monasteries, Danubian archaeological sites [14].

Overlapping documents submitted it follows that ethno-gastronomic specificities are directly proportional to the ethnic density (table 2). Depending on the dominance of one ethnic group within human settlements is highlighted a **touristic regionalization with gastronomic profile** (figure 3) in area of research, as follows:

- Rural settlements with **monovalent dominantly** potential (representing more than 10% of ethnic group): Ghindărești (Russian-Lippovans), Dobromir, Independența, Amzacea, Ciocârlia (Turks

-Tatars), Mihail Kogălniceanu (Aromanians);

- Rural settlements with **monovalent middle** potential (with a share between 5%-10% of ethnic group): Comana, 23 August, Mereni, Tuzla, Topraisar, Lipnița (Turks and Tatars);
- Rural settlements with **bivalent** potential (with a share over 1%, of ethnic group): Cobadin, Castelu, Cumpăna, Lumina, Agigea, Valu lui Traian (Turks-Tatars and Aromanians), Limanu (Turks-Tatars and Russian-Lippovans);
- Urban settlements with **monovalent** potential (representing more than 5% of ethnic group): Băneasa, Eforie, Murfatlar (Turks-Tatars);
- Urban settlements with **polyvalent** potential (with a share over 1%, of ethnic group): Constanța, Mangalia, Medgidia, Năvodari, Ovidiu, Techirghiol.

Fig. 3. Southern Dobrogea - the regionalization of touristic potential with gastronomic specific

It may be noted that the Dobrogea's cuisine was influenced by economic, geographical or climatic

factors, and the eating habits of various ethnic groups settled here in time, which permanently

enriched full cookbooks with recipes of some delicious dishes. After the First World War, while the development of resorts on Romanian seaside, the Dobrogea's cuisine it was greatly influenced by the European cuisine, dishes becoming fine, tasty and delicates and can rival with any other traditional cuisine [13].

Southern Dobrogea is an area that fascinates the traveler: although from the outside it does not seem appealing, in its depth, that is penetrating in its heart, knowing people and manners, you realize the geotouristic and cultural wealth, because in Dobrogea influences of Greek, Turkish-Tatar, Aromanians, Lippovans put their mark on the local gastronomy.

Fish preparations leading favorite among inhabitants from Southern Dobrogea, usually understandable, because of Danube and Black Sea bordering this region. Quick monitoring indicates some settlements and restaurants with fish specific: Mamaia and Constanța („*On Plonge*” restaurants), Agigea („*Pescăria lui Matei*”), 23 August - Olimp („*Cherhanaua*”, „*Lacul Racilor*”, „*Popasul Pescarilor*”), Limanu („*LifeHarbour*” complex). Other resources with gastronomic profile are valued in Constanța („*Balada Nej*” polyvalent traditional restaurant, Turkish restaurants), Eforie („*Nunta Zamfirei*”, Romanian traditional restaurant), Murfatlar (Wine Cellar and Touristic Point), Oltina (fishing touristic point) and Cumpăna („*Festival of Culinary Art*”). Please note that inhabitants also cook venison, mutton (especially Turks and Aromanians), beef, poultry or pork.

Among ethnic conglomerate currently living, **Turks** are the ones who most influenced the

cuisine in Dobrogea. A journey to the land between Danube and Black Sea cannot end without taste the delicious and famous *Dobrogea's pie* (it says that while knead, women sang love songs for husbands, because the pie out better), *Dobrogea's moussaka* or *Dobrogea's carp brine*, carefully prepared by housewives, in a traditional style, completing the Romanian culinary art.

Lippovans left Russia in the XVII-th century settled in Dobrogea, along Danube, putting a strong mark on traditional cuisine of present Dobrogea [13].

A specific feature is that they are often used in cooking *raisins*, *nuts* and *syrups* focused in areas influenced by Turkish culture. *Dairy* and *cheese* are also very popular, and *fruit*, *vegetables* and *eggs* are missing from Dobrogea's menu, which highlights the complexity of this cuisine, well structured by regions and subregions (figure 3).

In area of Southern Dobrogea can be established **touristic programs** with gastronomic or polyvalent specific, in order to exploit the touristic potential in rural areas, all year long, with greater frequency during summer for the tourists on the seaside. On Black Sea Coast and along Danube, the gastronomic specific is fishing type, Murfatlar and Ostrov vineyards are favorable to promotion enotourism and ethnic diversity is desirable for development of touristic programs with ethno-gastronomic profile. This can identify the following **touristic routes** (figure 4), with gastronomic profile.

Figure 4 shows some circuits and/or touristic routes with great potential, which are described in table 3.

Table 3. Circuits and touristic routes with polyvalent potential: ethno-gastro-touristic

Number	Gastronomic Route Type	Description of Route
1	<i>Sea fish Route</i>	Năvodari - Constanța - Eforie - Mangalia - Vama Veche, most development, with specific restaurants in Mamaia, Constanța, Agigea, Olimp and Limanu;
2	<i>Danube fish Route</i>	Ghindărești - Cernavodă - Oltina - Ostrov, with capitalization potential at Oltina;
3	<i>Southern Dobrogea's Wine Route</i>	Constanța - Murfatlar - Cernavodă - Ion Corvin - Ostrov, with Wine Cellars for tasting of wine at Murfatlar, Saligny and Ostrov;
4	<i>Ethno-gastronomy Route</i>	Constanța - Mihail Kogălniceanu (Aromanian specific) - Ghindărești (Lippovan specific); Constanța - Murfatlar - Cobadin, with ramifications to Băneasa and Independența (Turkish-Tatar specific); Constanța - Topraisar - Negru Vodă (Turkish-Tatar specific);
5	<i>Touristic Circuit with polyvalent gastronomic profile</i>	Constanța - Ovidiu - Murfatlar - Valu lui Traian - Constanța, with Romanian customs and Aromanian specific, Turkish-Tatar specific and enotouristic potential.

Fig. 4. Southern Dobrogea - Touristic routes with gastronomic profile

For each of circuits and routes mentioned can be made **specific offers**, where traditions and customs, be accompanied by Dobrogea's cuisine style or fishing and tasting wines from renowned vineyards of Dobrogea. A specialist in *gastronomy tourism* may carry *travel programs* focused on experiences to delight the taste and discovery of Dobrogea's local traditional culture.

It is remarkable the beginning of some events that shaped of a relevant *ethno-tourism* in Southern Dobrogea. The ethnic groups in this area are competing in the culinary skills at the "*Festival of Culinary Arts*" hosted by Cumpăna village, annually in September, since 2005, organized by Democratic Union of Turks and Tatars, attending representatives of several ethnic groups coexist in Dobrogea. The purpose of this event is to promote specific traditional cuisine of Dobrogea. Also, Cumpăna village is one of the finalists of the "*Romanian Cultural Village*" contest, held at the Village Museum in Bucharest, in order to promote cultural and touristic heritage in Romanian villages and achieved the third place in 2014.

Conclusions

1. The geotouristic relevance of Southern Dobrogea based on the combination of customs and traditions of ethnic groups with other local touristic resources, especially exploitation of gastro-tourism, as part of agri-tourism in the context of the proposed polyvalent circuits and touristic routes, all of which could contribute to developing bioeconomy with cultural and socio-economic sustainable values of rural space from area of research.
2. Geotouristic features of Southern Dobrogea are **the multicultural** due to the majority Romanian population and ethnic groups inhabiting (Aromanians, Turks, Tatars, Russian-Lippovans) and **diversified touristic potential** (Black Sea, lakes along Sea and Danube, protected areas, monasteries, historical sites, museums, traditional folk art, villages with Dobrogea's specific).
3. **Gastronomy tourism**, although relatively new in Romania as professionalized program has a niche of tourists with culinary interests of high potential, untapped at fair value. This segment of tourism market represents an opportunity for

travel agents and consultants, in South of Dobrogea and nationally level.

4. Southern Dobrogea has original and diverse gastronomic resources, but not enhanced, patchy and dispersed. Among gastronomic resources from this area, the most important for recovery are **fish**, especially marine, along Black Sea Coast and there are already several locations of interest, but still reserves untapped (especially regarding freshwater species in the area).

5. Developing on direction of resources gastronomic from Southern Dobrogea reveal optimal conditions for recovery by organizing **Guest Houses with ethno-gastronomic specific: Aromanian** (Mihail Kogălniceanu), **Russian-Lippovan** (Ghindărești), **Turkish-Tatar** (Băneasa, Cobadin, Independența, Dobromir, Amzacea), **multiethnic** (Cumpăna, Limanu, Castelu, Valu lui Traian), with **polyvalent** specific (Ostrov – monastic, fishing and wine tourism).

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News

Dear colleagues,

On behalf of the Organizing Committee of the **BIOATLAS International Conference**, it is our great pleasure and privilege to invite you to join us in Brasov, Romania, between 20-21 May 2016.

“BIOATLAS 2016” Conference provides a forum for food and tourism related professionals, professors, lecturers and PhD students to exchange information on education, research, applications and developments the Food and Tourism and publish the most recent results.

The topics include aspects related to Biodiversity and Agriculture technologies, New tendencies in Tourism development, IT&C in Agriculture, Food and Tourism Industry, etc. Contributions from various countries will allow a broadened perspective for all attending.

After the very successful meetings in **2006, 2008, 2010, 2012 and 2014**, **BIOATLAS 2016** offers us the opportunity to combine the beauty and hospitality of **Brasov** city with some of the outstanding works done on the important topics of food science and tourism, and to make easy contacts and relations among researchers from all around the world.

Braşov is probably the most beautiful city from Romania and one of the most important cities of Transilvania region, surrounded by the Southern Carpathians. Our city provides a mix of wonderful mountain scenery in the nearby Poiana Braşov, and medieval history with German influences in the old town.

Bioatlas 2016 will be held at the **Aula "Sergiu T. Chiriacescu"**, Transilvania University of Brasov. The building is an impressive conference center and is located near the historical city center.

We work closely with the Scientific Committee to provide an unforgettable scientific experience as well as to offer a social program filled with opportunities to share the beauty of Transilvania with colleagues and friends from all around the world in a very familiar and warm atmosphere.

We look forward to meet together in the spring of 2016 for a great Congress in Brasov!

Romulus Gruia, Liviu Gaceu

Chairs of the Organizing Committee